

DANS Data Station SSH FIP

Organization	FIP Wizard
Created by	Ricarda Braukmann (ricarda.braukmann@dans.knaw.nl)
Based on	FIP, 5.1.9 (gofair:FIP:5.1.9)
Project Phase	Defining FAIR Implementation Profile
Description	FIP for the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities
Created at	25 Jun 2026

Summary Report

Summary

Answered (current phase) 343 / 343

Answered 422 / 495

History of Versions

Version	Date	Changes
1.0.0	22 Jun 2026	
1.0.0	18 Jun 2026	
1.0.0	16 May 2026	
1.0.0	07 May 2026	
FIP Version Pre Update	08 Dec 2025	Versie van de FIP voordat er een update was met nieuwe velden.

I. About

FIP

A FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) is a list of declared technology choices intended to implement each of the FAIR Guiding Principles, made as a collective decision by the members of a particular community of practice. It thus lists FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs), a sub-class of FAIR Supporting Resources (FSR). The FIP is itself considered to be the implementation of R1.3, which is why there is no separate declaration addressing this subprinciple. The FIP questionnaire is augmented with explanations, per question, based on Jacobsen et al. FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations. Data Intelligence 2020; 2 (1-2): 10–29, [DOI](#) and referable at the [GO FAIR Foundation website](#).

As of version 5, the FIP also contains supporting declarations for the implementation of FSR that are not also FERs. These resources generally support Semantic Interoperability (SI). SI is at the heart of the FAIR principles and of the design of large scale cross disciplinary infrastructures. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a European-wide effort towards such an infrastructure. The EOSC Semantic Interoperability Task Force drafted a questionnaire focusing on recommendations for SI (EOSC SI Task Force) with the ambition to converge on globally relevant and scalable SI solutions for EOSC (<https://doi.org/10.5281%2Fzenodo.8028392>).

In this questionnaire you can create a FIP to provide a comprehensive, integrated profile for implementing both FAIR principles and semantic interoperability. This profile is itself captured as a FAIR (machine-readable) dataset and is made openly available to other communities for reuse. To create a profile, the data steward of a community needs to fill out this questionnaire where the implementation choices are recorded as resources. The questionnaire is structured as follows: the first section is about the FAIR Implementation Community, which is then followed by a number of questions per FAIR principle. The answer to each of the declaration questions should be a FER. In the case of supporting declarations, it should be a different type of FSR. The questionnaire offers to look up the resource in Nanodash. If the resource cannot be found in any of these applications, there is an option at the end of the questionnaire to register an FSR as a nanopublication in Nanodash. The resource will get a PURL which can then directly be used when further filling out the questionnaire. Over time, profiles will need to be revised to reflect the evolving needs of the community and the ongoing development of FAIR technologies. The FIP Wizard helps to make FAIRification efforts more structured, better informed and overall more efficient.

The FIP Wizard has a number of features specifically supporting FIP creation:

Navigation: While creating the profile, the questionnaire can be navigated using the navigation tool on the left side of the page.

Versioning: The FIP Wizard has versioning that allows systematic revisions of completed profiles over time which in turn can provide insight into FAIR-related technology trends.

Nanopublications: The FIP Wizard makes use of a data format called nanopublications to capture profiles as FAIR data (in this case, as FAIR Digital Objects). In some cases, it may be necessary to author original nanopublications to complete your profile. The FIP Wizard supports the creation of original nanopublications in Chapter VII, "Register a new resource as a nanopublication".

Detailed instructions for completing the FIP Wizard questionnaire can be found [here](#).

FIP Wizard team is composed of Barbara Magagna, Marek Suchanek, Tobias Kuhn, Erik Schultes, Dario Bijker, and Gerhard Burger. We would like to acknowledge the generous support of CODATA and ENVRI-FAIR. We wish you success in composing your FIP. If you have any comments, questions or suggestions on how to improve the FIP Wizard experience, [contact us](#).

The FIP Wizard has its origin in the [GO FAIR FAIR Convergence Matrix \(& FIP\) Working Group](#) and development has been supported by the Center for Digital Scholarship at the Leiden University Libraries, CODATA, the ENVRI-FAIR project, the enthusiastic participation of numerous FAIR Implementation Communities, [see](#).

For further reading: Reusable FAIR Implementation Profiles as Accelerators of FAIR Convergence. In: Grossmann G., Ram S. (eds) Advances in Conceptual Modeling. ER 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 12584. Springer, Cham, [DOI](#).

Supporting links:

- [GO FAIR Community interpretation of FAIR](#)
- Summary of [type definitions of FAIR Enabling Resources](#)
- [How to GO FAIR](#)
- [Request a FIP Workshop](#)

Summary

Answered (current phase)	0 / 0	
Answered	0 / 0	

Questions

No questions

II. Metadata for your FAIR Implementation Profile

Implementing the FAIR Principles requires numerous choices concerning the use of FAIR-Enabling Resources, be they commitments to domain-relevant standards or to infrastructure technologies. These collective decisions compose the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP), and are made on behalf of that community of practice.

A FAIR Implementation Community (FIC) is defined as a voluntary association of people and organisations that agree to adhere to the same FIP. Note, the FAIR Implementation Community can be large or small, formal or informal. It is anticipated that FIPs will likely evolve (merge, split) over time as they are designed, tested and repurposed by other FICs. In any case, the FIC is fundamentally important to FAIR and defining the FIC is the beginning of any FAIRification effort.

In this section of the FIP Wizard, you, the Community Data Steward, are requested to answer questions that will declare, in a machine-readable way, the FAIR Implementation Community.

Summary

Answered (current phase)	6 / 6	
Answered	9 / 9	

Questions

1

Select your FAIR Implementation Community

In the drop-down list, select your FAIR Implementation Community. If your community is not yet listed, you will need to first create a nanopublication referencing your FAIR Implementation Community. Once you create this nanopublication, you will then see it in the drop-down list. A Wizard for creating nanopublications referencing a FAIR Implementation Community can be accessed below (in Chapter VII. Register a new resource as a nanopublication).

Managers DANS Data Station SSH

This FIP is created by the managers of the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) to provide an overview of the FAIR Implementation Choices of the DANS Data Station SSH.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA508adujnSK418WRLX5OgfUeWh5cA0pqc3UqXyMGhaeU/Managers-DANS-DataStationSSH>

2

Who is the main point of contact for this FAIR Implementation Profile?

As the main point of contact, you take the responsibility for reporting on the collective decisions taken by your community to implement the FAIR Principles.

Answers

2.a.1

Please add your ORCID

Provide the ORCID here (like this: 0000-0003-2195-3997, without <https://orcid.org/>).

✓ 0000-0001-6899-760X

2.b.1

Please add your ORCID

Provide the ORCID here (like this: 0000-0003-2195-3997, without <https://orcid.org/>).

✓ 0000-0001-6383-7148

2.c.1

Please add your ORCID

Provide the ORCID here (like this: 0000-0003-2195-3997, without <https://orcid.org/>).

✓ 0000-0003-4532-1273

3

Select the type of digital object you are focusing on in this FIP

This question is not necessarily required to be answered, as in some contexts the community of interest might be offering a service for others.

In any other case, please make sure the answers in this FIP are fitting to the specific choice of digital object type. If digital objects from multiple types are created by the community we ask you to make a clone of this FIP and change the FAIR Enabling Resources where needed.

If you can't find the right term in the drop-down list, please **mint a digital object type of your choice as a nanopublication [template](#)**. Once you create this nanopublication, you will then see it in the drop-down list.

Data

Facts, measurements, recordings, records, or observations about the world, collected by researchers, that are yet to be processed/interpreted/analysed. Data may be in any format or medium taking the form of writings, notes, numbers, symbols, text, images, films, video, sound recordings, pictorial reproductions, drawings, designs or other graphical representations, procedural manuals, forms, diagrams, work flow charts, equipment descriptions, data files, data processing algorithms, or statistical records.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/gff/rao/terms/Data>

4

If you have, please provide an accessible identifier of one of your digital objects of the chosen type.

✓ <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-z4c-tctq>

5

Link to a case study

You might find it useful to link this FIP to a specific case study which is a description of a data problem in a real-life situation. The case study should provide the context necessary to support recognition of gaps to be addressed; demonstrate the value of adoption; or to inform future developments. It should contain a brief description of the (research, societal, technical) goals that the case study wants to achieve, as well as user stories. It is recommended to use this [template](#) for creating a new case study within the FIP-Wizard. Alternatively, links to case study descriptions (e.g. in [OSF](#) or in [Zenodo](#)) are also accepted.

✓ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7867779>

6

Please indicate the version of this FIP

Use semantic versioning syntax (<https://semver.org/>). The three positions (1.2.3) stand for different types of changes:

1. for a new decision on FSR composition decided by the community;
2. for required changes of FSRs related to curation needs;
3. for small metadata changes in the FIP. Please do not forget to change the version when you publish the FIP.

✓ 1.0.0

III. Declarations for Findability

Digital resources should be easy to find for both humans and computers. Extensive machine-actionable metadata are essential for automatic discovery of relevant datasets and services, and are therefore an essential component of the FAIRification process.

*Answer the questions below using the drop-down lists to select the FAIR Enabling Resources your community uses to implement the FAIR Principles. You will see that many of the FAIR Enabling Resources in the drop-down list are associated with a GO FAIR Foundation Qualification badge. GFF Qualified Resources have been assessed for their compliance with the preliminary Qualification Criteria of the GO FAIR Foundation (referenced in Chapter 1: About). If you do not find the FAIR Enabling Resources you are looking for in the drop-down list, it will be necessary to register that Resource as a nanopublication. To do so, access the nanopublication Wizard in Chapter VII, "Register a new resource as a nanopublication". Once you create a nanopublication referencing your FAIR Enabling Resource, it will automatically become visible and selectable in the drop-down lists of the FIP Wizard. In addition to selecting FAIR Enabling Resources from the drop-down list, you are also asked to comment on status of the implementation (radio buttons) and to leave a free-text "consideration" that records the basis for these implementation choices (such as various requirements or constraints that impact your community). *

Summary

Answered (current phase)	77 / 77	
Answered	101 / 107	

Questions

1

Declaration F1 Metadata: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?

Principle F1 states that digital resources, i.e., data and metadata, must be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier which serves as a permanent machine interpretable reference. The GO FAIR Foundation emphasizes the need for persistence and global uniqueness, as well the property of resolvability of the identifiers (see also A1). Globally unique means that the identifier is guaranteed to unambiguously refer to the intended resources (where 'global' is means 'universal' as there are described digital assets outside the 'world'). Therefore, it is insufficient for it to be unique only locally (e.g. unique within a single, local database). Persistence refers to the requirement that this globally unique identifier is never reused in another context, and continues to identify the same resource over time, even if that resource should no longer exist, or moves from one digital environment to another. While global uniqueness is a technical property (i.e., an algorithm that can guarantee with mathematical precision that the issued identifiers are unique), persistence is a social commitment made by the stakeholder responsible for issuing the identifiers, that these identifiers will continue to map to the objects they identify for a defined period of time. An additional property supported by the GO FAIR Foundation is that the identifier is also 'resolvable' by machines. An identifier is most useful in a large-scale automated environment only when it can be resolved into (i.e., linked to) the object it identifies. Furthermore, the GO FAIR Foundation also assumes predictable identifier resolution behavior, allowing identifier resolution to behave consistently across multiple requests. Taken together, the GO FAIR Foundation assumes FAIR implementations to have Globally Unique, Persistent and Resolvable Identifiers (GUPRIs).

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type "identifier service" which is a service that provides for metadata (1) algorithms guaranteeing global uniqueness, (2) policy document that guarantees persistence and (3) resolution of the identifier to machine-actionable metadata describing the object and its location.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✓ We use DOIs provided by DataCite for the DANS Data Station SSH as this is one of the most common PIDs used in the research repository field. It should be noted that in the repository (that is based on Dataverse) the DOI refers to the landing page where the metadata of the datasets can be found as well as where access to the data is requested. In a way the DOI refers to both the data and the associated metadata and the division between a PID for the metadata and a PID for the data as suggested by this and the following question is not present in our data repository.

2

Declaration F1 Data: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?

Principle F1 states that digital resources, i.e., data and metadata, must be assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier which serves as a permanent machine interpretable reference. The GO FAIR Foundation emphasizes the need for persistence and global uniqueness, as well the property of resolvability of the identifiers (see also A1). Globally unique means that the identifier is guaranteed to unambiguously refer to the intended resources (where 'global' is means 'universal' as there are described digital assets outside the 'world'). Therefore, it is insufficient for it to be unique only locally (e.g. unique within a single, local database). Persistence refers to the requirement that this globally unique identifier is never reused in another context, and continues to identify the same resource over time, even if that resource should no longer exist, or moves from one digital environment to another. While global uniqueness is a technical property (i.e., an algorithm that can guarantee with mathematical precision that the issued identifiers are unique), persistence is a social commitment made by the stakeholder responsible for issuing the identifiers, that these identifiers will continue to map to the objects they identify for a defined period of time. An additional property supported by the GO FAIR Foundation is that the identifier is also 'resolvable' by machines. An identifier is most useful in a large-scale automated environment only when it can be resolved into (i.e., linked to) the object it identifies. Furthermore, the GO FAIR Foundation also assumes predictable identifier resolution behavior, allowing identifier resolution to behave consistently across multiple requests. Taken together, the GO FAIR Foundation assumes FAIR implementations to have Globally Unique, Persistent and Resolvable Identifiers (GUPRIs).

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type "identifier service" which is a service that provides for data (1) algorithms guaranteeing global uniqueness, (2) policy document that guarantees persistence and (3) resolution of the identifier to machine-actionable metadata describing the object and its location.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

National Bibliography Number (NBN)

National Bibliography Number (NBN) is a group of publication identifier systems used by national libraries in countries such as Germany, Italy, Finland, Norway, The Netherlands and Sweden.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAqf81e8IXfuh_LXONePCOANNizY0HsQhF1GdboHqqI2o/URN:NBN

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- Next to DOIs, datasets in the DANS data station SSH can also be identified by a URN:NBN. All datasets do have a DOI. Not all datasets do have an URN:NBN. Often only new deposited datasets do get an URN:NBN.

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite DOI Resolution Service Fabrica

Fabrica is DataCite's web interface where you can create, find, connect and track all of your DOIs and metadata. Fabrica also includes all of the functionalities needed to manage repository accounts, prefixes and contacts.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RATn3tHBIrq3NMNC67hGGrwX4v18uhr7uaBwRT1krJEHs#DataCite_Doi_Resolution_Service

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of

Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

2.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use DOIs provided by DataCite for DANS Data Station SSH as this is one of the most common Persistent Identifiers used in the research repository field. The DOI refers to the

landing page where the metadata of the datasets can be found as well as where access to the datasets is requested. In a way the DOI refers to both the datasets and the associated metadata and the division between a PID for the metadata and a PID for the datasets as suggested by this and the following question is not present in our data repository. A dataset consists of one or more individual files. The individual files have an internal identifier (a unique number) that enable the retrieval of the files.

3

Supporting Declaration F1: Which Persistency Policy do you use for Identifiers?

A Persistency Policy is a policy with respect to persistency of resources.

✓ b. Supporting Declaration: FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Supporting Resource

DANS Data Station Policy

The scope of the DANS Data Stations Policy (“the Policy”) is limited to datasets for which DANS performs ingestion, curation, archiving, long-term preservation, and dissemination. Such datasets are stored and managed in the repository services referred to as a ‘DANS Data Station’, which combines a public facing, domain specific repository based on Dataverse software where the datasets are managed and made accessible, and a service referred to as ‘the Vault’ where datasets are archived for long-term preservation. The Policy does not consider archiving and preservation of other materials, such as DANS’s web pages, internal and external documents, and digital objects in any other services that DANS provides. The Policy governs the obligations, responsibilities, and expectations of the role players.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RASdbrWz5cwX0gOUoM3A03T2c293LbG7dAN9_NoZsOTXU/DANS_DataStationPolicy

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The DANS Data Station Policy contains the following implementation consideration: "All published datasets are provided with a persistent identifier (PID) that resolves to the landing page of the dataset in a Data Station."

Declaration F2: What metadata schema do you use for findability?

Whereas principle F1 enables unambiguous identification of resources of interest, principle F2 speaks to the ability to discover a resource of interest through, for example, search or filtering. Digital resources must be described with rich metadata – including descriptors of the content of the resource referred to by that identifier. It is hard to generally define the minimally required “richness” of this metadata, except that the more generous and comprehensive it is, both for humans and computers, the more specifically findable (in a meaningful way) it becomes in refined searches. Descriptive metadata are, therefore, extremely important in cross-domain search and interdisciplinary use cases [see for example, OAIS, ISO 14721:2012; Lee, 2010]. For centuries, it has been common practice in the scholarly community to clearly reference research results through citations. To enable findability, the metadata required for citations is the minimum requirement and a number of works have defined the required properties (creator, title, publication date, publisher, and identifier) in a variety of documents [Data Citation Synthesis Group, 2014, Ball & Duke, 2015; Mooney & Newton, 2012 and Fenner et al., 2019]. Other works defined additional core metadata requirements for data discovery which may serve as a guideline [Asmi et al., 2017, DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2019, Loscio et al., 2017 and Albertoni et al., 2020]. Community specific metadata requirements, for examples those created in Metadata for Machine (M4M) workshops, may include additional metadata properties. While other principles specify metadata elements that must be present to support, for example, specific aspects of reusability (e.g. citation and license), principle F2 is primarily about discovery - that a digital resource that is well-described can be easily discovered even when the resource is unknown to the agent performing the search. Thus, this principle encourages data providers and domain experts to consider the various facets of search that might be employed by a user of their data, and to support those users in their discovery of the resource. To enable both global and local search engines to locate a resource, generic and domain-specific descriptors should be provided, that can be exposed to indexing by the relevant search facilities.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “metadata schema” which is a specification (schema) that defines metadata fields describing attributes of data or other digital objects.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)**4.b.1****List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)****Answers****4.b.1.a.1****Select the FAIR Enabling Resource**

The Dublin Metadata Element Set, which is often called Dublin Core (DC), is a standardized metadata scheme for description of any kind of resource such as documents in electronic and non-electronic form, digital materials (such as video, sound, images, etc) and composite media like web pages. Dublin Core Metadata may be used for multiple purposes, from simple resource description, to combining metadata vocabularies of different metadata standards, to providing interoperability for metadata vocabularies in the Linked Data cloud and Semantic Web implementations. Please note that this version of the specification for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1 is somewhat out of date, although it is not officially deprecated. The DCMI Metadata Terms specification is linked to this record and is the current documentation that should be used for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RApwFvegOdPfNuKlF64wctAzaffAv3j_2kAU9y6kfBoy8#DCMI

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Our data repository system Dataverse allows for the creation of different metadata blocks and fields and the metadata can be exported into various schemas. The metadata includes Dublin Core fields.

4.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DDI-Codebook is a more light-weight version of the standard, intended primarily to document simple survey data. Originally DTD-based, DDI-C is also available as an XML Schema.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RA31wDwlAlgw1f9EXCLzqUNyY-MSMHJ3VE-SMb4zIRQA#DDI-Codebook>

4.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Our data repository system Dataverse allows for the creation of different metadata blocks and fields and the metadata can be exported into various schemas. We include a metadata block that contains fields from DDI as these are recommended to be included when documenting social sciences studies. We follow the recommendation of CESSDA - the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives - in the choice of the fields we include in our metadata.

4.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Schema.org Dataset

Metadata schema contained in a catalog

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAfpqlmxNsTJLDAV3ZvcQBoddyZf-Yhl2WHXFpGHOLe-Y#Schema.org_Dataset

4.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Our data repository system Dataverse allows for the creation of different metadata blocks and fields and the metadata can be exported into various schemas. The metadata can be exported in schema.org.

4.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archives

The OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archive provides instruction for data archive managers to expose their metadata in a way that is compatible with the OpenAIRE infrastructure. The metadata from data archives should be included in the OpenAIRE information space, and exposed when data are related to an open access publication e.g. a dataset cited by an article.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.123197>

4.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Our data repository system Dataverse allows for the creation of different metadata blocks and fields and the metadata can be exported into various schemas. We follow the guidelines by OpenAIRE when choosing which metadata fields to include.

4.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DCAT-AP | Data Catalog Vocabulary Application Profile for Data Portals in Europe

DCAT-AP is a specification based on the Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT) developed by W3C and provides a common specification for describing public sector datasets in Europe to enable the exchange of descriptions of datasets among data portals.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAGhCnj_zKSZURRm5MgkkeLAnGfGYp3Bw_he3pYS4k0o4#DCAT-AP

4.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

4.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

The Croissant Metadata Format

Croissant is a new metadata format for ML-ready datasets. Croissant was developed collaboratively by a community from industry and academia, as part of the MLCommons effort. The Croissant format doesn't change how the actual data is represented (e.g., image or text file formats) — it provides a standard way to describe and organize it. Croissant builds upon schema.org, the de facto standard for publishing structured data on the Web, which is already used by over 40M datasets. Croissant augments it with comprehensive layers for ML relevant metadata, data resources, data organization, and default ML semantics.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA4FPVI6QaUIGUpxz2Ghk0Rx0o2hZaASTMRyEhI38KfqQ#Croissant>

4.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

4.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite Metadata Scheme

The DataCite Metadata Schema is a list of core metadata properties chosen for accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes, with recommended use instructions in the documentation. The resource that is being identified can be of any kind, but it is typically a dataset. We use the term 'dataset' in its broadest sense. We mean it to include not only numerical data, but any other research objects in keeping with DataCite's mission (<https://datacite.org/value.html>). The metadata schema properties are presented and described in detail in the section DataCite Metadata Properties in this document.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAko0U2Q8boW-drM8t11DcbX6lXu2mcSQf-2BrM07gelQ#datacite_metadata_scheme

4.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

5

Supporting Declaration F2: What metadata editor service do you use?

An editor is a service that provides user-friendly interface for easy editing of metadata, vocabularies and crosswalks.

✓ b. Supporting Declaration: FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Supporting Resource

Dataverse Editor

Dataverse functions as a comprehensive metadata editor (and repository) for research data. It allows users to create, edit, and manage detailed metadata at both the dataset and file levels, supporting metadata standards.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAS9OhmH4DZOqQGwAmPcVP_jSIIPes5GbUwp4_4XbjTIQ/Dataverse_editor

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use Dataverse software which offers the possibility to publish and edit metadata.

6

Supporting Declaration F2: What validation service do you use for provided metadata?

A validation service is a system that verifies the accuracy, completeness, or compliance of data, code or processes against predefined criteria or standards.

- ✓ a. Supporting Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

6.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

Declaration F3: What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?

separated from the actual resource they describe, but are nonetheless persistently linked via a GUPRI (linking metadata explicitly to the resource and vice versa, as described in FDOF specifications). Here we explicitly emphasize that implementation choice as crucial for a FAIR by design approach. The F3 principle states that any description of a digital resource must contain clearly and explicitly the identifier of that resource being described. For instance, the description of a computational workflow, should explicitly contain the identifier for that workflow in a manner that is unambiguous (well qualified, see Principle I3). This is especially important where the resource and its metadata are stored independently, but are nonetheless persistently linked, which is assumed to be the case by the GO FAIR Foundation. The purpose of this principle is twofold. First, it is perhaps trivial to say that a descriptor should explicitly say what resources it is describing; however, there is a second, less-obvious reason for this principle. Many digital objects (such as workflows, as mentioned above) have well-defined structures that may disallow the addition of new fields, including fields that could point to the metadata about that resource. Therefore, the only consistent way for both humans and machines to discover the metadata of a resource is through a search for the identifier of that resource. Thus, by requiring that a metadata descriptor contains the identifier of the thing being described, that identifier may then successfully be used as the search term to discover its metadata record. However, it should be clear that in many cases the identifier itself is not a regular search term. In fact the GO FAIR Foundation considers it good practice in FAIR to avoid semantic meaning in GUPRIs as these are be prone to change. That is why rich metadata are already defined in F2 of the guiding principles. When FAIR principle F3 mentions that the identifier of the object should be explicitly and clearly included in the object's metadata, our interpretation assumes "explicit" refers to the mere presence of the resources's identifier in the content of the metadata record while "clear" refers to having this identifier directly and unambiguously related to the metadata record by means of a known predicate. In previous experiments examining common usage, we have identified over 20 different ways that stakeholders sometimes use to declare which resource is being described by a given metadata record. This makes it very hard for humans and machines to, given a metadata record, identify which object this record describes.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type "metadata-data linking schema" which is a specification that provides a unique, persistent, (ideally) bi-directional, machine-actionable link between metadata and the data they describe.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)**7.b.1****List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)**

Answers

7.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

RO-Crate | Research Object Crate

RO-Crate is a community effort to establish a lightweight approach to packaging research data with their metadata. It is based on schema.org annotations in JSON-LD. An RO-Crate is a structured archive of all the items that contributed to the research outcome, including their identifiers, provenance, relations and annotations.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAQy_EWHjCh-ARWWzc44pR1JeFilxFQyNYNt-_lyflkQM#RO-Crate

7.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- c. Is planned to be used in the future

7.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

8

Declaration F4 Metadata: Which service do you use to publish your metadata records?

Principle F4 states that digital resources must be registered or indexed in a searchable resource (e.g., a search engine). The searchable resource provides the infrastructure by which a metadata record (made accessible with a GUPRI, F1) can be discovered, using either the attributes in that metadata (F2) or via the identifier of the resource itself (F3) [T. Weigel , U. Schwardmann , J. Klump , S. Bendoukha & R. Quick . Making data and workflows findable for machines. Data Intelligence 2(2020), 40–46. 10.1162/dint_a_00026].

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “registry” which is a service that indexes metadata and data and provides search over that index.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

8.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

8.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DANS Data Station-Social Science and Humanities (SSH)

This Data Station enables deposit data and search for data within the social sciences and humanities domains. The metadata of the Data Station SSH is also available in the national ODISSEI portal and the European CESSDA Data Catalogue (see the DANS website).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAIqEwiWjd3U9d8BTPMr1-CdiK4IQfj37z8DyQtRHTBc#DANS-Data-Station-SSH>

8.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Our metadata is published through our Dataverse-based Data Station SSH. Dataverse is an open source repository software that our institute has experience with through our service DataverseNL and we are able to contribute to the development of the service together with the Global Dataverse Community.

8.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OpenAIRE Research Graph

The OpenAIRE Research Graph is an open resource that aggregates a collection of research data properties (metadata, links) available within the OpenAIRE Open Science infrastructure for funders, organizations, researchers, research communities and publishers to interlink information by using a semantic graph database approach. There are a number of interfaces available for the research graph, including OpenAIRE Explore, a knowledgebase which makes the content of the OpenAIRE Research Graph publicly available.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAQKm4e3E9TS7hFhm0OkRpKjLZEIE6pGpXHIDH3mrJ9vE#OpenAIRE>

8.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The metadata from the Data Station can be harvested and is included in OpenAIRE to improve the findability of the datasets. OpenAIRE is a large European infrastructure that facilitates the search for scholarly communication and we find it important to be included in the OpenAIRE infrastructure.

8.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Google Dataset Search

Google Dataset Search is a search engine from Google that helps researchers locate online data that is freely available for use.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAUhotKhSj2m1ftHGPXAYyL2QgY60L6mYrunOzQwGZJ44#Google_Dataset_Search

8.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The Data Station can be indexed by Google Dataset Search to increase the findability of the datasets.

8.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Google Search

Google indexes billions of web pages to allow users to search for the information they desire through the use of keywords and operators.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAmIZNVGWc2awqZYQGesFtPXS3wUAIQxMd1MUjgJK1j3M#Google>

8.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The Data Station can be indexed by Google Dataset Search to increase the findability of the datasets.

8.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Harvard Dataverse Repository

Harvard Dataverse Repository is a research data repository running on the open source Dataverse software. The repository is fully open to the public, allows upload and browsing of data from all fields of research, and is free for all researchers worldwide.

Harvard Dataverse Repository receives support from Harvard University, public and private grants, and an emergent consortium model.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.t2e1ss>

8.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Harvard Dataverse maintains an overview of all Dataverse installations including the Data Station SSH. The inclusion of our Data Station increases the findability of our datasets.

8.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

B2FIND

B2FIND gathers diverse metadata on the research output of many heterogeneous sources, with the aim of providing a unified discovery portal allowing widespread and cross-disciplinary search and access to the underlying data collections.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RARKGmoA6jLQnUvkijvsoS6zcXxbiujviU39B54DoH208#B2FIND>

8.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The metadata from the Data Station can be harvested and is included in B2Find to increase the findability of the datasets.

8.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite Commons

DataCite Commons is a search engine for work, people, organisations, and repositories. By the time this FER is created, it is not functioning correctly with 403 errors.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAYW_D8gGAdgo68ygWQHMQQDaeoETuMMhNjBs0xdQR58s#DataCite-Commons

8.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The metadata from the Data Station can be harvested and is included in the DataCite Commons to increase the findability of our datasets.

8.b.1.h.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Mendeley Data

Mendeley Data is a multidisciplinary, free-to-use open repository specialised for research data. Files of any format can be uploaded and shared with the research community following the FAIR data principles, up to a maximum of 10GB per dataset. Each version of a dataset is given a unique DOI, and dark archived with DANS (Data Archiving and Networking Services), ensuring that every dataset and citation will be valid in perpetuity. Datasets can be licensed under a range of open licences, and datasets are and will continue to be free access. Mendeley Data supports embargoing of data both generally and while undergoing peer review. It is funded by a subscription model for Academic & Government entities.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3epmpp>

8.b.1.h.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.h.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The metadata from the Data Station can be harvested and is included in Mendely Data to increase the findability.

8.b.1.i.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ODISSEI Portal

The ODISSEI Portal is a metadata repository running on the open source DataVerse software developed by the Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations (ODISSEI), the research infrastructure for the social sciences in the Netherlands.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAcv6GezhLQWkYxGltQo_UBVRUJdmroqGkxFSJVOtqXDg#ODISSEI_Portal

8.b.1.i.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.i.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The metadata from the Data Station can be harvested and is included in the ODISSEI Portal. The ODISSEI Portal is a Dutch national initiative from the Open Data Infrastructure for Social

Science and Economic Innovations (ODISSEI) which aims to make Dutch social science datasets findable within one interface.

8.b.1.j.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CESSDA Data Catalogue

The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) Data Catalogue contains descriptions (metadata) of the more than 30,000 data collections held by CESSDA's Service Providers (SP), representing 20 European countries. It is a one-stop shop for searching and finding data, enabling effective access to European social science data. The data described are varied. They may be quantitative, qualitative or mixed-modes data, cross-sectional or longitudinal, recently collected or historical data.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a12316>

8.b.1.j.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.j.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- The metadata from the Data Station can be harvested and is included in the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC). The CDC collects metadata from all CESSDA archives to allow researchers to search for social science datasets across all European Social Science data archives.

8.b.1.k.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CLARIN VLO | CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory

The Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) faceted browser was developed within CLARIN as a means to explore linguistic resources, services and tools available within CLARIN and related communities.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAvoZ390GAR8Sd36P1ZMEo1TCe8-PAM4hF80j_0tNu-UQ#CLARIN-VLO

8.b.1.k.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.k.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The metadata from the Data Station can be harvested and is included in CLARIN. CLARIN is the Infrastructure for Language resources.

8.b.1.l.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CLARIAH Media Suite

The CLARIAH Media Suite is the central digital access point for AV collections and search and analysis tools in the Netherlands for students and researchers. It is part of the Dutch

Infrastructure for Digital Humanities and Social Science developed in the CLARIAH project. The full version of the Media Suite is accessible to researchers and students from Dutch universities, higher education institutions and a select number of Dutch research institutions.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAZX7L1-w9rDC-Cl-dGdJJQUH7xBdqEaO4dABpv7u4TWQ/CLARIAH-Media-Suite>

8.b.1.l.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.l.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ A set of metadata related to Oral History are available in the CLARIAH Media Suite. CLARIAH is the Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities and the Media Suite is one of the CLARIAH research environments. Our oral history datasets are included in this environment to increase their findability.

8.b.1.m.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Getuigenverhalen

Getuigenverhalen is a website that keeps the stories and personal testimonies about the Second World War.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RA4e_LwRPfdYKYXI5NJY7_tAsvptgmEkGI8JMIxdz629U#Getuigenverhalen

8.b.1.m.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

8.b.1.m.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ A set of metadata related to oral histories of the Second World War are available in the portal "Getuigenverhalen"

9

Declaration F4 Datasets: Which service do you use to publish your datasets?

Principle F4 states that digital resources must be registered or indexed in a searchable resource (e.g., a search engine). The searchable resource provides the infrastructure by which a metadata record (made accessible with a GUPRI, F1) can be discovered, using either the attributes in that metadata (F2) or via the identifier of the resource itself (F3) [T. Weigel, U. Schwardmann, J. Klump, S. Bendoukha & R. Quick. Making data and workflows findable for machines. Data Intelligence 2(2020), 40–46. 10.1162/dint_a_00026].

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type "registry" which is a service that indexes metadata and data and provides search over that index.

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

9.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

9.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DANS Data Station-Social Science and Humanities (SSH)

This Data Station enables deposit data and search for data within the social sciences and humanities domains. The metadata of the Data Station SSH is also available in the national ODISSEI portal and the European CESSDA Data Catalogue (see the DANS website).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAIqEwiWjd3U9d8BTpMr1-CdiK4IQfj37z8DyQtRHTBc#DANS-Data-Station-SSH>

9.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

9.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- We use our Data Station SSH based on Dataverse to publish our datasets. Dataverse is an open source repository software that our institute has experience with through our service DataverseNL and we are able to contribute to the development of the service together with the Global Dataverse Community.

10

Supporting Declaration F4: Which Persistency Policy do you use for repositories?

A Persistency Policy is a policy with respect to persistency of resources.

✓ b. Supporting Declaration: FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

10.b.1

List the FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

Answers

10.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Supporting Resource

DANS Data Station Policy

The scope of the DANS Data Stations Policy ("the Policy") is limited to datasets for which DANS performs ingestion, curation, archiving, long-term preservation, and dissemination. Such datasets are stored and managed in the repository services referred to as a 'DANS Data Station', which combines a public facing, domain specific repository based on Dataverse software where the datasets are managed and made accessible, and a service referred to as 'the Vault' where datasets are archived for long-term preservation. The Policy does not consider archiving and preservation of other materials, such as DANS's web pages, internal and external documents, and digital objects in any other services that DANS provides. The Policy governs the obligations, responsibilities, and expectations of the role players.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RASdbrWz5cwX0gOUoM3A03T2c293LbG7dAN9_NoZsOTXU/DANS_DataStationPolicy

10.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

10.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The DANS Data Stations Policy describes how the repository service is organized and what steps DANS takes to preserve the data and metadata entrusted to us.

IV. Declarations for Accessibility

Typically, the purpose of identifying a digital resource is to simultaneously provide the ability to retrieve the record of that resource, in some format, using some clearly-defined mechanism. Principle A1 asserts that there should be no additional barrier to the retrieval of the record by a computational agent when its access protocol (A1.1 & A1.2) results in permitted access to that record. Note that the agent may be a machine working behind a firewall, if that agent has been permitted access. For fully mechanized access, this requires that the identifier (F1) follows a globally-accepted schema that is tied to a standardized, high-level communication protocol. FAIR, however, does not necessarily preclude non-mechanized access, only that the mechanism is so well described that a machine can identify the appropriate next course of action even if it should include human agents. In the latter case, it is still necessary that the identifier (F1) be sufficient as a way of unambiguously indicating, to a non-automated agent, the record that is being requested. The “standardized communication protocol” is critical here. Its purpose is to provide a predictable way for an agent to access a resource, regardless of whether the access to the content of the resource is open or restricted, and regardless of whether that access is automated or aided by human action (e.g., “send your request for access by email or telephone”). Bottom line, protocols for retrieving digital resources should be made explicit, for both humans and machines, including well-defined mechanisms to obtain authorization for access to protected data.

Summary

Answered (current phase)	43 / 43	
Answered	56 / 60	

Questions

1

Declaration A1.1 Metadata: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?

The protocol (schema) by which a digital resource is accessed (e.g. queried) should not pose any bottleneck. It describes an access process, hence does not directly pertain to restrictions that apply to using the resource. The protocols underlying the World-Wide Web, such as HTTP, are an archetype for an open, free, and universally implementable protocol. Such protocols reduce the cost of gaining access to digital resources, because they are well defined and open and allow any individual to create their own standards-compliant implementation. That the access to the protocols specifications is free ensures that those lacking monetary means can equitably access the specifications and can implement them without incurring in any monetary obligations. That it is universally implementable ensures that the technology is available to all (and not restricted, for instance, by country or a sub-community), thus encompassing both the 'gratis' and 'libre' meaning of 'free'.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type "communication protocol" which is a specification that defines how messages are structured and exchanged.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

REST | Representational state transfer

REST defines a set of constraints for how the architecture of an Internet-scale distributed hypermedia system, such as the Web, should behave.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAszH6LU-Zc3UO7MHPKj1Lb0dmMmaTJrRvQ0jqpXMyFY4#REST>

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ REST is the basis of the native Dataverse API.

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

HTTPS | Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure

Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) is an extension of the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). It is used for secure communication over a computer network, and is widely used on the Internet. In HTTPS, the communication protocol is encrypted using Transport Layer Security (TLS) or, formerly, Secure Sockets Layer (SSL). The protocol is therefore also referred to as HTTP over TLS, or HTTP over SSL

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAF1ANn-BCFop0OBMOC7S8NtG0y_xYhRX4tAu37XZVCo0#HTTPS

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OAI-PMH Schema | Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema

The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema (OAI-PMH Schema) provides a formal structure for validating responses as part of the OAI-PMH Protocol. The OAI-PMH Protocol is a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability. Data Providers are repositories that expose structured metadata via OAI-PMH. Service Providers then make OAI-PMH service requests to harvest that metadata. OAI-PMH is a set of six verbs or services that are invoked within HTTP.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAnwFn9lcKK8S2tccnwPZjw-0_hF5N03BL-8BuchPHtvQ#OAI-PMH

1.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Dataverse supports the harvesting of metadata through the OAI-PMH harvesting protocol.

1.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SWORD | Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit (SWORD) API (v2.0)

SWORD stands for “Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit” and is a “profile” of AtomPub (RFC 5023) which is a RESTful API that allows non-Dataverse Software to deposit files and metadata into a Dataverse installation. Client libraries are available in Python, Javascript, Java, R, Ruby, and PHP. The SWORD API was formerly known as the “Data Deposit API” and was introduced in Dataverse Network (DVN) 3.6.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RARo-Jl6-z6G-wVk636iGn-Zz8_amE8-7RnqaSrBwM5mg#SWORD-API-v2.0

1.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ SWORD is being used to transfer data and metadata from a source to our repository. It is used for machine-to-machine interactions.

1.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Dataverse API | The Dataverse Software APIs

The Dataverse Software APIs allow users to accomplish many tasks such as creating datasets, uploading files, publishing datasets, and much, much more, all without using the Dataverse installation's web interface.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAHz8Om-r8FUQKyB411E9u5peAXmF0c1tkZNqQ_MEEpEE#DataverseAPI

1.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration A1.1 Datasets: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?

The protocol (schema) by which a digital resource is accessed (e.g. queried) should not pose any bottleneck. It describes an access process, hence does not directly pertain to restrictions that apply to using the resource. The protocols underlying the World-Wide Web, such as HTTP, are an archetype for an open, free, and universally implementable protocol. Such protocols reduce the cost of gaining access to digital resources, because they are well defined and open and allow any individual to create their own standards-compliant implementation. That the access to the protocols specifications is free ensures that those lacking monetary means can equitably access the specifications and can implement them without occurring in any monetary obligations. That it is universally implementable ensures that the technology is available to all (and not restricted, for instance, by country or a sub-community), thus encompassing both the 'gratis' and 'libre' meaning of 'free'.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type "communication protocol" which is a specification that defines how messages are structured and exchanged.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

REST | Representational state transfer

REST defines a set of constraints for how the architecture of an Internet-scale distributed hypermedia system, such as the Web, should behave.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAszH6IU-Zc3UO7MHPKj1Lb0dmMmaTJrRvQ0jqpXMyFY4#REST>

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ REST is the basis of the native Dataverse API.

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

HTTPS | Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure

Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) is an extension of the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). It is used for secure communication over a computer network, and is widely used on the Internet. In HTTPS, the communication protocol is encrypted using Transport Layer Security (TLS) or, formerly, Secure Sockets Layer (SSL). The protocol is therefore also referred to as HTTP over TLS, or HTTP over SSL

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAF1ANn-BCFop0OBMOC7S8NtG0y_xYhRX4tAu37XZVCo0#HTTPS

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SWORD | Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit (SWORD) API (v2.0)

SWORD stands for “Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit” and is a “profile” of AtomPub (RFC 5023) which is a RESTful API that allows non-Dataverse Software to deposit files and metadata into a Dataverse installation. Client libraries are available in Python, Javascript, Java, R, Ruby, and PHP. The SWORD API was formerly known as the “Data Deposit API” and was introduced in Dataverse Network (DVN) 3.6.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RARo-Jl6-z6G-wVk636iGn-Zz8_amE8-7RnqaSrBwM5mg#SWORD-API-v2.0

2.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ SWORD is being used to transfer data and metadata from a source to our repository. It is used for machine-to-machine interactions.

2.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Dataverse API | The Dataverse Software APIs

The Dataverse Software APIs allow users to accomplish many tasks such as creating datasets, uploading files, publishing datasets, and much, much more, all without using the Dataverse installation's web interface.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAHz8Om-r8FUQKyB411E9u5peAXmF0c1tkZNqQ_MEEpEE#DataverseAPI

2.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Supporting Declaration A1.1: What Web-API do you use to interact with created metadata instances?

- ✓ b. Supporting Declaration: FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Supporting Resource

Dataverse Web API

The Dataverse Data Access API provides programmatic download access to the files stored in a Dataverse installation. More advanced features of the Access API include format-specific transformations (thumbnail generation/resizing for images; converting tabular data into alternative file formats) and access to the data-level metadata that describes the contents of the tabular files.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA0R3SoMJlBUf1ni1OgjU14w3TgnRMx80YD7dvAPyLiqo/DataverseWebAPI>

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use Dataverse software which includes a set of APIs. More information in the API guide <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/api/>

4

Declaration A1.2 Metadata: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?

This principle clearly demonstrates that following the FAIR guiding principles is not equal to making all data 'open'. Some digital resources, such as data that have access restrictions based on ethical, legal or contractual constraints, require additional conditions/steps to be accessed. This often pertains to assuring that the access requester is indeed that requester (authentication), that the requester's profile and credentials match the access conditions of the resource (authorization), and that the intended use matches permitted use cases (e.g. for a particular purpose only) (see also R1.1, where there are requirements to provide explicit documentation about who may use the data, and for what purposes). At the level of technical implementation, an additional authentication and authorization procedure must be specified, if it is not already defined by the protocol (see A1.1). A requester can be a human or a machine agent. In the latter case it is probably a proxy for a human or an organization to which the authentication and authorization protocol should be applied, in which case, the machine should be expected to present the appropriate credentials. The principle requires that a FAIR resource must provide such a protocol, but the protocol itself is not further specified. In practice, an Internet of FAIR Data and Services cannot function without implementing Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, which includes AAI for machines and should thus be Ontology-based and machine actionable (see also Christopher Brewster, Barry Nouwt, Stephan Raaijmakers, Jack Verhoosel; Ontology-based Access Control for FAIR Data. *Data Intelligence* 2020; 2 (1-2): 66–77. [DOI](#)).

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “authentication and authorization service” which is a service that mediates access to digital objects according to specified conditions.

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

4.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

5

Declaration A1.2 Datasets: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?

This principle clearly demonstrates that following the FAIR guiding principles is not equal to making all data 'open'. Some digital resources, such as data that have access restrictions based on ethical, legal or contractual constraints, require additional conditions/steps to be accessed. This often pertains to assuring that the access requester is indeed that requester (authentication), that the requester's profile and credentials match the access conditions of the resource (authorization), and that the intended use matches permitted use cases (e.g. for a particular purpose only) (see also R1.1, where there are requirements to provide explicit documentation about who may use the data, and for what purposes). At the level of technical implementation, an additional authentication and authorization procedure must be specified, if it is not already defined by the protocol (see A1.1). A requester can be a human or a machine agent. In the latter case it is probably a proxy for a human or an organization to which the authentication and authorization protocol should be applied, in which case, the machine should be expected to present the appropriate credentials. The principle requires that a FAIR resource must provide such a protocol, but the protocol itself is not further specified. In practice, an Internet of FAIR Data and Services cannot function without implementing Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, which includes AAI for machines and should thus be Ontology-based and machine actionable (see also Christopher Brewster, Barry Nouwt, Stephan Raaijmakers, Jack Verhoosel; Ontology-based Access Control for FAIR Data. *Data Intelligence* 2020; 2 (1-2): 66–77. [DOI](#)).

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “authentication and authorization service” which is a service that mediates access to digital objects according to specified conditions.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SURFconext

SURFconext offers secure access everywhere with one set of credentials. It lets your users log in to all the cloud services your institution uses with one username and password. Both for services that everyone uses and services for small specialist teams. Secure, easy and privacy-friendly.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA6rPajWW-RQsdrKg65htqgvU0a5efiqKaQIEBXcKicU#SURFconext>

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ SURFConext is a service that connects (Dutch) institutions to service providers, it is offered by SURF is a cooperative association of Dutch educational and research institutions providing IT services for the education and research community.

5.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Gmail Log In

Gmail is a mailbox provider by Google

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA7NTEjj8Zhi0NmXh6f4hBNzjOzm2bL-uBSxjN5i7d7Ww/>
[Gmail](#)

5.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Dataverse offers the possibility to login with a Google account which can be used as an alternative if a individual does not posses an institutional account to log in via SURFConext.

5.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

FAIR-enabling resource: ORCID-AAI | Open Researcher and Contributor ID AAI service

ORCID is an open, non-profit, community-driven effort to create and maintain a registry of unique researcher identifiers and a transparent method of linking research activities and outputs to these identifiers. The ORCID Registry is a repository of unique researcher identifiers which allows researchers to manage a record of their research activities. In addition, there are APIs that support system-to-system communication and authentication.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAnf2hj1w4rywAclhA_R0vx54K-OJNGdUjyeycfWF6i0#ORCID-AAI

5.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The Data Stations offer the possibility to login with an ORCID account.

5.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Dataverse Access Request Service

A Dataverse installation account can be created with the Username/Email log in option, using the "Sign Up" page.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RA84mrDX7-kS9tpnuG7FGaEh6aOWX1qjsfNmJ_oRk0toc/DataverseAccessRequestService

5.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✓ Datasets which are not openly available but rather available under "restricted access" can be requested by a user by submitting an access request. This request is then evaluated by the depositor of the dataset who can grant or reject access to the individual. Dataverse provides mechanisms for the process and we have implemented this as many depositors want or need to restrict access to their datasets for instance in case of personal data or sensitive information.

5.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Github Login

GitHub login is the process of authenticating using credentials used to access Github.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAev60yLKJrodAbXI5cKPMQ4GruzuEVe9bkFPu4OUQR0/GithubLogin>

5.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

Declaration A2: What metadata preservation policy do you use?

There is a continued focus on keeping relevant digital resources available in the future. Data may no longer be accessible either by design (e.g. a defined lifespan within limited financial resources or legal requirements to destroy sensitive data) or by accident. However, given that those data may have been used and are referenced by others, it is important that consumers (including machines) have, at the very least, access to high quality and machine actionable metadata that describes those resources sufficiently to minimally understand their nature and their provenance, even when the relevant data are not available anymore. This principle relies heavily on the “second purpose” of principle F3 (the metadata record contains the identifier of the data), because in the case where the data record is no longer available, there must be a clear and precise way of discovering its historical metadata record. This aspect of accessibility is further elaborated in the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles [M. Martone . Data citation synthesis group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. San Diego CA FORCE11, no. principle 6, 2014. 10.25490/a97f-egykh].

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “metadata preservation policy” which is a document that describes the conditions under which metadata are to be provisioned in the future (generally part of a data management plan).

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

6.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

6.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements for Certification

The CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements reflect the characteristics of trustworthy repositories. As such, all Requirements are mandatory and are equally weighted, standalone items. Although some overlap is unavoidable, duplication of evidence sought among Requirements has been kept to a minimum where possible. The CoreTrustSeal, launched in 2017, defines requirements and offers core level certification for Trustworthy Data Repositories holding data for long-term preservation. It is the culmination of a cooperative effort between the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) and the World Data System of the International Science Council (WDS), under the umbrella of the Research Data Alliance (RDA), to harmonize their data repository certifications. The CoreTrustSeal Requirements describe the characteristics required to be a trustworthy repository for digital data and metadata. Each Requirement is accompanied

by Guidance text describing the response statements and evidence that applicants must provide to enable an objective review. Applicants must respond to all of the Requirements.

Note: The 2017 original recommendations from the "RDA Repository Audit and Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG", who became a maintenance group on 19th April 2022, changed its name to CoreTrustSeal Maintenance WG. The previously named group, Repository Audit and Certification DSA-WDS Partnership WG, finished its term under RDA and delivered its outputs. For those with an interest in the topic of certification, please visit/join the parent Interest Group: RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.469e84>

6.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

6.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We have received CoreTrustSeal (CTS) application for our Data Station SSH and Archaeology. CTS is an international, community based, non-governmental, and non-profit organization promoting sustainable and trustworthy data infrastructures and offers data repositories a core level certification.

V. Declarations for Interoperability

When two or more digital resources are related to the same topic or entity, it should be possible for machines to automatically merge the information into a richer, unified view of that entity. Similarly, when a digital entity is capable of being processed by an online service, a machine should be capable of automatically detecting this compliance and facilitating the interaction between the data and that tool. This requires that the meaning (semantics) of each participating resource – be they data and/or services service – is clear.

*Answer the questions below using the drop-down lists to select the FAIR Enabling Resources your community uses to implement the FAIR Principles. You will see that many of the FAIR Enabling Resources in the drop-down list are associated with a GO FAIR Foundation Qualification badge. GFF Qualified Resources have been assessed for their compliance with the preliminary Qualification Criteria of the GO FAIR Foundation (referenced in Chapter 1: About). If you do not find the FAIR Enabling Resources you are looking for in the drop-down list, it will be necessary to register that Resource as a nanopublication. To do so, access the nanopublication Wizard in Chapter VII, "Register a new resource as a nanopublication". Once you create a nanopublication referencing your FAIR Enabling Resource, it will automatically become visible and selectable in the drop-down lists of the FIP Wizard. In addition to selecting FAIR Enabling Resources from the drop-down list, you are also asked to comment on status of the implementation (radio buttons) and to leave a free-text "consideration" that records the basis for these implementation choices (such as various requirements or constraints that impact your community). *

Summary

Answered (current phase)	155 / 155	
Answered	190 / 230	

Questions

1

Declaration I1 Metadata: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?

Consumers spend a disproportionate amount of time trying to make sense of the digital resources they need and designing accurate ways to combine them. This is most often due to a lack of suitably unambiguous content descriptors, or a lack of such descriptors entirely with respect to non-machine-interpretable data formats such as tables or “generic” XML. Community-defined data exchange formats work reasonably well within their original scope of a few types of data and a relatively homogeneous community, but not well beyond that. This makes interoperation and integration an expensive, often impossible task (even for humans), but also means that machines cannot efficiently make use of digital resources, which is the primary goal of the FAIR guiding principles. For example, when a machine visits two data files in which a field “temperature” is present, then it will need more contextual descriptions to distinguish between weather data in one file and body temperature measurements in another. Achieving a “common understanding” of digital resources through a globally understood “language” for machines is the purpose of principle I1, with an emphasis on “knowledge” and “knowledge representation”. This becomes critical when many differently formatted resources need to be visited or combined across organizations and countries and is especially challenging for interdisciplinary studies or for meta-analyses, where results from independent organizations, pertaining to the same topic, must be combined. In this context, the principle says that producers of digital resources are required to use a language (i.e., a representation of data/knowledge) that has a defined mechanism for mechanized interpretation – a machine-readable “grammar” – where, for example, the difference between an entity, as well as any relevant relationship between entities, is defined in the structure of the language itself. This allows machines to consume the information with at least a basic “understanding” of its content. It is a step towards a common understanding of digital resources by machines, which is a prerequisite for a functional Internet of FAIR Data and Services. Several technologies can be chosen for principle I1.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “knowledge representation language” which is a language specification whereby knowledge can be made processable by machines.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

JSON-LD is a JSON-based format to serialize Linked Data. The syntax is designed to easily integrate into deployed systems that already use JSON, and provides a smooth upgrade path from JSON to JSON-LD. It is primarily intended to be a way to use Linked Data in Web-based programming environments, to build interoperable Web services, and to store Linked Data in JSON-based storage engines. JSON-LD is a concrete RDF syntax. A JSON-LD document is both an RDF document and a JSON document and correspondingly represents an instance of an RDF data model. However, JSON-LD also extends the RDF data model to optionally allow JSON-LD to serialize generalized RDF Datasets.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAQKjgd7Ug9xSo4J0REW_AHGOJyaF9-ydj60nunqQ0qVg#JSON-LD

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Metadata can be exported in JSON-LD format

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CROISSANT Metadata Format

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAEf6lxpb63KYHMO8jxjM_lqefzyvBCflaRBe_80K3Gck/CROISSANT

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OpenAIRE Metadata Schema for Data Archives

The OpenAIRE Guidelines for Data Archive Managers 2.0 will provide instruction for data archive managers to expose their metadata in a way that is compatible with the OpenAIRE infrastructure. The metadata from data archives should be included in the OpenAIRE information space, and exposed when data are related to an open access publication e.g. a dataset cited by an article.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAeruj17umsX8Vz0FbgObnWy4vt7fbkkGMbZAF5T4OC2I/OpenAIRE_Metadata_Schema_for_Data_Archives

1.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ OpenAIRE Metadata Schema for Data Archives is one of the export metadata formats of DANS Data Station SSH

1.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Data Documentation Initiative Codebook | DDI-Codebook

Data Documentation Initiative (DDI-Codebook, DDI-C) is a more light-weight version of DDI-Lifecycle, intended primarily to document simple survey data. Originally DTD-based, DDI-C is now available as an XML Schema. The freely available international DDI standards describe data that result from observational methods in the social, behavioral, economic, and health sciences. DDI is used to document data in over 80 countries of the world.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.EZCpPd>

1.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ DDI Codebook is one of the export metadata formats of DANS Data Station SSH

1.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Dublin Core Metadata Element Set | DCES

The Dublin Metadata Element Set, which is often called Dublin Core (DC), is a standardized metadata scheme for description of any kind of resource such as documents in electronic and non-electronic form, digital materials (such as video, sound, images, etc) and composite media like web pages. Dublin Core Metadata may be used for multiple purposes, from simple resource description, to combining metadata vocabularies of different metadata standards, to providing interoperability for metadata vocabularies in the Linked Data cloud and Semantic Web implementations. Please note that this version of the specification for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1 is somewhat out of date, although it is not officially deprecated. The DCMI Metadata Terms specification is linked to this record and is the current documentation that should be used for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1. This document, an excerpt from the more comprehensive document "DCMI Metadata Terms" [DCTERMS] provides an abbreviated reference version of the fifteen element descriptions that have been formally endorsed in the following standards: ISO Standard 15836:2009 of February 2009 [ISO15836], ANSI/NISO Standard Z39.85-2012 of February 2013 [NISOZ3985], and IETF RFC 5013 of August 2007 [RFC5013].

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3nx7t>

1.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Dublin Core Metadata Element Set is one of the export metadata formats of DANS Data Station SSH

1.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

JSON | JavaScript Object Notation

JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) is a lightweight, text-based, language-independent data interchange format. It was derived from the ECMAScript Programming Language Standard. JSON defines a small set of formatting rules for the portable representation of structured data. This RFC specification aims to remove inconsistencies with other specifications of JSON, repair specification errors, and offer experience-based interoperability guidance.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAypIT9C-q0n_Y2tOPqCOM19ETJNWdvNI40rVF11AMoiw#JSON

1.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ JSON is one of the export metadata formats of DANS Data Station SSH

2

Declaration I1 Datasets: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?

Consumers spend a disproportionate amount of time trying to make sense of the digital resources they need and designing accurate ways to combine them. This is most often due to a lack of suitably unambiguous content descriptors, or a lack of such descriptors entirely with respect to non-machine-interpretable data formats such as tables or “generic” XML. Community-defined data exchange formats work reasonably well within their original scope of a few types of data and a relatively homogeneous community, but not well beyond that. This makes interoperation and integration an expensive, often impossible task (even for humans), but also means that machines cannot efficiently make use of digital resources, which is the primary goal of the FAIR guiding principles. For example, when a machine visits two data files in which a field “temperature” is present, then it will need more contextual descriptions to distinguish between weather data in one file and body temperature measurements in another. Achieving a “common understanding” of digital resources through a globally understood “language” for machines is the purpose of principle I1, with an emphasis on “knowledge” and “knowledge representation”. This becomes critical when many differently formatted resources need to be visited or combined across organizations and countries and is especially challenging for interdisciplinary studies or for meta-analyses, where results from independent organizations, pertaining to the same topic, must be combined. In this context, the principle says that producers of digital resources are required to use a language (i.e., a representation of data/knowledge) that has a defined mechanism for mechanized interpretation – a machine-readable “grammar” – where, for example, the difference between an entity, as well as any relevant relationship between entities, is defined in the structure of the language itself. This allows machines to consume the information with at least a basic “understanding” of its content. It is a step towards a common understanding of digital resources by machines, which is a prerequisite for a functional Internet of FAIR Data and Services. Several technologies can be chosen for principle I1.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “knowledge representation language” which is a language specification whereby knowledge can be made processable by machines.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Portable Document Format (PDF)

The Portable Document Format (PDF), standardized as ISO 32000, is a file format developed by Adobe in 1992 to present documents, including text formatting and images, in a manner independent of application software, hardware, and operating systems. Based on the PostScript language, each PDF file encapsulates a complete description of a fixed-layout flat document, including the text, fonts, vector graphics, raster images and other information needed to display it.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAuxR5Gx_uvvBVoePV226Lk86VRYrh9EpmqFXU7f_ojQ#pdf

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ PDF/A is preferred format. see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

TXT | text file

kind of computer file containing plain text (description from <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q86920>)

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAT7RQ0uzSMeQ5tznGfIA7v35NC4CFQegZvUWlsfptBzE#TXT>

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Unicode text (txt) see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

HTML: The HyperText Markup Language

The HyperText Markup Language or HTML is the standard markup language for documents designed to be displayed in a web browser. It is often assisted by technologies such as Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and scripting languages such as JavaScript. Web browsers receive HTML documents from a web server or from local storage and render the documents into multimedia web pages. HTML describes the structure of a web page semantically and originally included cues for its appearance.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAVoliicDuWm0TCWvcpXlo5PoA7RdCv8WVDwdtYUuAEVc#HTML>

2.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

NetCDF | Network Common Data Form

Unidata's Network Common Data Form (netCDF) is a set of software libraries and a machine-independent data format that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data. This record describes the data format and not the software libraries. The netCDF Data Model is also a community standard for sharing scientific data. The data model of dimensions, variables, and attributes, which define the The Classic Model, was extended starting with netCDF-4.0. The new The Enhanced Data Model supports the classic model in a completely backward-compatible way, while allowing access to new features such as groups, multiple unlimited dimensions, and new types, including user-defined types. For maximum interoperability with existing code, new data should be created with the The Classic Model. The Classic Model was introduced with the very first netCDF release, and is still the core of all netCDF files.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAdLEtlqBBprmFUyN3rnpq_30o8G35R95_YqNYEdKmX6M#NetCDF

2.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CSV File Format

Files with .csv (Comma Separated Values) extension represent plain text files that contain records of data with comma separated values. Each line in a CSV file is a new record from the set of records contained in the file. Such files are generated when data transfer is intended from one storage system to another. Since all applications can recognize records separated by comma, import of such data files to database is done very conveniently. Almost all spreadsheet applications such as Microsoft Excel or OpenOffice Calc can import CSV without much effort. Data imported from such files is arranged in cells of a spreadsheet for representation to user.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAcNC9zQOEc9RPXD07R91aMNSlYmjR9G4kRT_Pm4FpzkE#CSV

2.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

IBM SPSS Statistics Data File Format

IBM® SPSS® Statistics data files are files specifically formatted for use by IBM SPSS Statistics, containing both data and the metadata (dictionary) that define the data.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAvcKpl_g4CLWb_VubkXEvSGcKu96WU3irchqgfdyUAGg#SPSS-Format

2.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Stata Data File Format (.dta)

Stata data files are saved with the extension “.dta”. This means the file is ready to use in Stata and unlike data saved in, for example, an excel file, you do not need to import this into Stata. Stata is a general-purpose statistical software package developed by StataCorp for data manipulation, visualization, statistics, and automated reporting.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAotwwEgkd0DyOp6D6fMkGAmiUdxp8PIQ4F5WC8vSHihc#Stata>

2.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.h.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

****R File Format ****

R File Format most often used by the R Studio

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAyw_pe27xoto8fkWHU7X_LjUY8-zj39weh-7krx8t7FA#R-File-Format

2.b.1.h.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.h.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.i.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

JPEG File Format

JPEG is a commonly used method of lossy compression for digital images, particularly for those images produced by digital photography. The file might have a .jpg or .jpeg extension.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAqJhu6LHwidmg3dB7vGx6JIEM_3U2g6sKntmGasocCak#jpeg

2.b.1.i.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.i.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.j.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Tag Image File Format (TIFF)

A TIFF is a computer file used to store raster graphics and image information. The file might have either a .tiff or .tif extension.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAi2XqkUsg08QLQ6HuS7PXHREjruRsfCTpr7oFSMR3dPl#tiff>

2.b.1.j.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.j.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.k.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Portable Network Graphics (PNG)

PNG is a raster-graphics file format that supports lossless data compression. PNG files use the file extension .png and have been assigned the MIME media type image/png.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAeQ9BaFx_qAuhqOmsg4EG0QjIV8fsr4X0cL2SYLZsxo#png

2.b.1.k.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.k.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.l.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

JPEG File Format

JPEG is a commonly used method of lossy compression for digital images, particularly for those images produced by digital photography. The file might have a .jpg or .jpeg extension.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAqJhu6LHwidmg3dB7vGx6JIEM_3U2g6sKntmGasoccak#jpeg

2.b.1.1.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.1.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ JPEG 2000 see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.m.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ASCII | American Standard Code for Information Interchange

ASCII (American Standard Code for Information Interchange) is the most common character encoding format for text data in computers and on the internet. In standard ASCII-encoded data, there are unique values for 128 alphabetic, numeric or special additional characters and control codes.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RABvAt9gnw5TPlzgnVAbhQF-OQvGmUMxoxHiQwBioeS2c#ASCII>

2.b.1.m.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.m.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ ASCII GRID see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.n.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

LASer (LAS) File Format | .las

The LAS file format is a public file format for the interchange of 3-dimensional point cloud data between data users. Although developed primarily for exchange of lidar point cloud data, this format supports the exchange of any 3-dimensional x,y,z tuple. This binary file format is an alternative to proprietary systems or a generic ASCII file interchange system used by many companies. The LAS file format is a binary file format that maintains information specific to the lidar nature of the data while not being overly complex.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAyvzVOxxGvWZn2SS5Z7r2ylZLCMz8467OV02nqRyiR0Q#LAS>

2.b.1.n.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.n.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.o.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

LAZ File Format | .laz

The LAZ file format is a compressed version of the LAS (Lidar LASer) file format, which is specifically designed for storing lidar point cloud data. LAZ files retain the same data and structure as LAS files but employ lossless compression techniques to reduce file size while preserving the original data fidelity. The LAZ file format was developed to address the growing demand for efficient storage and transmission of large lidar datasets. By compressing LAS files, LAZ files significantly reduce their size, making them easier to manage and transfer. The compression is achieved by employing a combination of different algorithms, such as entropy coding and variable-length encoding, to represent lidar point attributes in a more compact form. Despite the compression, LAZ files retain the ability to fully restore the original LAS data without any loss of information. This means that once a LAZ file is decompressed, it can be processed and analyzed in the same way as an uncompressed LAS file. The compression and decompression process is typically performed using specialized software or libraries that support the LAZ format. The LAZ file format maintains compatibility with LAS files, ensuring interoperability across lidar software and processing tools. This means that applications that can read and process LAS files can typically handle LAZ files without any modifications.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAp4CdEee3KyWxwSbH_Wk33YbIRPDWgpEotCdToU3IYac#LAZ

2.b.1.o.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.o.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.p.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

RDF | Resource Description Framework

The Resource Description Framework (RDF) is a framework for representing information in the Web.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAutRQwoS4d5eLq7eBV1xsnWZ2spDYH4xfhhRzOxSZdhs#RDF>

2.b.1.p.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.p.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.q.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Turtle Format

Turtle is a common textual syntax for RDF that allows an RDF graph to be completely written in a compact and natural text form, with abbreviations for common usage patterns and datatypes.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RACae-ljg14EaVYyTAMCtNltLR8DW8Bqr3W3Z6f3SmTvM#Turtle>

2.b.1.q.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.q.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.r.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

JSON-LD | JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data

JSON-LD is a JSON-based format to serialize Linked Data. The syntax is designed to easily integrate into deployed systems that already use JSON, and provides a smooth upgrade path from JSON to JSON-LD. It is primarily intended to be a way to use Linked Data in Web-based programming environments, to build interoperable Web services, and to store Linked Data in JSON-based storage engines. JSON-LD is a concrete RDF syntax. A JSON-LD document is both an RDF document and a JSON document and correspondingly represents an instance of an RDF data model. However, JSON-LD also extends the RDF data model to optionally allow JSON-LD to serialize generalized RDF Datasets.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAQKjgd7Ug9xSo4J0REW_AHGOJyaF9-ydj60nunqQ0qVg#JSON-LD

2.b.1.r.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.r.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.s.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

REFI-QDA (Qualitative Data Analysis)

The purpose of the REFI-QDA (Qualitative Data Analysis) standard is to enable the exchange of qualitative data between QDA programs. The standard has been developed by QDA software companies ATLAS.TI, Dedoose, f4 analysis, MAXQDA, NVivo, QDAMiner, Quirkos and Transana. The standard consists of two parts: REFI-QDA Codebook, for exchanging codebooks. REFI-QDA Project for the exchange of information about projects. The specifications of the REFI-QDA standard are openly available and the format is based on XML. See: <https://www.qdasoftware.org>. The REFI-QDA (Qualitative Data Analysis) standard is a preferred format for file type Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis (CAQDAS).

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RA-g3dlGgzdTKVU7npt_ARMtUiYS1BIPqeOnl0BHikPBo/REFI-QDA

2.b.1.s.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.s.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ see: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/>

2.b.1.t.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Open Document Format

The OpenDocument format for file formats has been developed by the Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS) as XML-based open standards for storing and exchanging various types of data. OpenDocument was incorporated as an official ISO standard on 11 November 2006. This standard is further elaborated in OpenDocument 1.1 (1 February 2007) and OpenDocument 1.2 (29 September 2011). The file formats are in fact ZIP compression files within which XML files and any additions such as images have been collected. The free Apache OpenOffice software uses OpenDocument formats as standard formats. Outside of this package, OpenDocuments enjoy good support. Microsoft Office has supported OpenOffice formats since version 2007, although problems may occur with specific properties of the OpenDocuments. In many countries, including the Netherlands, the use of open source software and OpenDocuments has been set as standard for making government documentation accessible. OpenDocument formats are suitable for archiving, accessibility and reusability in the long term. The OpenDocument format for text documents is OpenDocument Text (.odt). ODT is a preferred format under the Text documents file type.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RACWIZCVgoa5kBIWp-HrL0BJ3Q9olrJrzS71yb4zWR2Cs/ODT>

2.b.1.t.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.t.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.u.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

eXtensible Markup Language (XML)

Extensible Markup Language (XML) is a simple, very flexible text format derived from SGML (ISO 8879). Originally designed to meet the challenges of large-scale electronic publishing, XML is also playing an increasingly important role in the exchange of a wide variety of data on the Web and elsewhere.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAQLETXaxPTEvZdt7Cx761TwcHLzBKPF3J6bM5YCY2IIY#XML>

2.b.1.u.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.u.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.v.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Markdown

Markdown is a lightweight markup language that is known for its simplicity and ease of use for writing structured documents. It was created in 2004 by John Gruber, with significant contributions from Aaron Swartz. Gruber wanted to create a plain-text format that could be easily converted to structurally valid HTML. His goal was to develop a syntax that was both human-readable and easy to write, as opposed to the verbose nature of HTML. The resulting Markdown consists of two components: a plain text formatting syntax, and a software tool that converts the plain text to HTML. The first Markdown version was released as an open-source project and was quickly adopted by bloggers and people working with wikis. Today it is widely used by platforms like GitHub (as README files), Reddit, Stack Overflow, and Discord.

Markdown's readability and ease of use make it popular in a variety of domains, including web content creation, software documentation, note-taking and manuscript writing. It allows bloggers, journalists, developers and authors to create documents for the web without needing a deep understanding of HTML or CSS, as Markdown files can easily be converted into fully formatted documents. While Markdown is widely used, there isn't a universally accepted standard specification for its syntax. The exact implementation can differ across platforms and versions. Markdown parsers and implementations may interpret the same input differently, leading to potential difficulties when moving content across platforms or converting them into different formats. For example, certain Markdown features, such as code blocks, images and footnotes, may be rendered differently on Github versus a personal website using a different Markdown processor. Note that these rendering differences don't affect the content of the Markdown file, just the layout.

Interpretations can also differ across different Markdown parsers. This has led to the

development of slightly different Markdown syntax variations that you can refer to as flavors or dialects. The vast majority of the syntax will be the same across dialects, so don't worry about it too much. The dialects may differ in which features are supported (such as tables or math blocks), and may handle ambiguities differently. DANS accepts any markdown dialect. A Markdown document can have a .md or .markdown extension. Markdown is a preferred file format for file type Markup Language.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAuaL32uEOj8AW2VFDogV4Gvjzj4twQk4RxGDhO4t9Gio/Markdown>

2.b.1.v.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.v.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.w.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Matlab

MATLAB is a programming platform designed specifically for engineers and scientists. The heart of MATLAB is the MATLAB language, a matrix-based language allowing the most natural expression of computational mathematics. The name MATLAB stands for matrix laboratory. MATLAB was originally written to provide easy access to matrix software developed by the LINPACK and EISPACK projects, which together represent the state-of-the-art in software for matrix computation. MATLAB has evolved over a period of years with input from many users. In university environments, it is the standard instructional tool for introductory and advanced courses in mathematics, engineering, and science. In industry, MATLAB is the tool of choice for

high-productivity research, development, and analysis. This format is accepted in DANS with no further conversions required in its executable code format (.m) and its workspace files (.mat). We strongly suggest to build up your code as neatly as possible and clearly state which version of MATLAB was used to develop the code, include comments where necessary, and make use of good programming practices. The code should be clear enough for users to understand the results and for possible reproduction of the study and methods. MATLAB is a preferred format for file type Programming languages.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAAYhmXMNiFEGwWdDm3HRFr-QVapaQ3eWhznI5LBwdA7c/Matlab>

2.b.1.w.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.w.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.x.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Text-Fabric

Files in the text-fabric file format (.tf) store a column of feature values that correspond to nodes and edges in a graph, which together represent annotated text. So, one could say that .tf is a Markup format. Annotated Text In the humanities, primary research data often takes the form of texts. Many of these texts are historical artefacts and a lot of knowledge is needed to interpret them. Annotations are a preferred way to represent this knowledge. They may convey detailed linguistic information at the word level, but they can also link persons, places, materials, and concepts found in the text to external descriptions. Texts are always structured, and annotations

need an addressing mechanism to target the specific portions in the text that they are about. The annotations tend to form bodies of knowledge in themselves, and need to be shared and distributed as separate entities. Data model Text-Fabric is a tool that facilitates this exchange of data. In order to do so, it defines a model [TF model] for annotated text. In this model, text is an annotated graph: a system of nodes and edges between nodes, where nodes and edges are linked to other information by means of features. The nodes stand for textual concepts, such as words, sentences, chapters, and the edges for relationships between these portions of text. Features are mappings from nodes or edges to values. Nodes themselves are just integer numbers, and edges are just pairs of numbers. This model is very close to Linguistic Annotation Framework [LAF ISO standard]. The main differences are that LAF prefers to be represented in XML and Text-Fabric is XML-free, and that a LAF dataset may reside in a single or in separate files at the choice of the corpus designer, while a Text-Fabric dataset always stores a single feature in a single file. Node features A node feature is a mapping from numbers to values: a column of values, where the position in the column corresponds to the number of the node. Edge features An edge feature can be seen as a mapping from nodes to other nodes, where a value may be supplied for each connection. Edge features are also columns of values, where the position in the column corresponds to the number of the node where the edges start. File format Text-Fabric defines an efficient way to store features in files [TF file format]. Each feature occupies a single file. A Text-Fabric dataset is just a flat collection of feature files. Extension Feature files typically have extension .tf . Tools Text-Fabric is also a library [TF API] by which you can process text and annotations. It understands the .tf file format and offers an API to load and save feature files and to compute with the data contained in them. Text-Fabric compiles .tf files into binary .tfx files which are optimised to load very fast. These .tfx files are just a convenience but are not suitable for archiving and should not be considered a preferred or even acceptable format. They are dependent on the computer where they have been generated. Text-Fabric is by no means required to make sense of .tf files. The format is so transparent that several users bypass the tool Text-Fabric and have written their own programs (in languages other than Python) to ingest .tf files. Corpora A number of corpora [TF Corpora] have already been converted to Text-Fabric, such as the Hebrew Bible, various Cuneiform tablet collections, the Quran, and more. For all these corpora there are dedicated tutorials [TF tutorials] that show the practice that Text-Fabric supports. References TF model: Model – Text-Fabric (archived version) TF file format: Format – Text-Fabric (archived version) TF optimizations: Optimizations – Text-Fabric (archived version) TF example: Banks: convert.ipynb (archived version) TF API: TF – Text-Fabric (archived version) TF Corpora: Corpora – Text-Fabric (archived version) TF Tutorials: tutorials (archived version) LAF ISO Standard: ISO 24612:2012 – Linguistic annotation framework (LAF) Text-Fabric is a preferred format for file type Programming languages.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAINA2BC5xWhd9sK-yGKeRBCLHL8vtS6_CNC1nj6MIWus/Text-Fabric

2.b.1.x.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.x.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.y.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Open Document Format

The OpenDocument format for file formats has been developed by the Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS) as XML-based open standards for storing and exchanging various types of data. OpenDocument was incorporated as an official ISO standard on 11 November 2006. This standard is further elaborated in OpenDocument 1.1 (1 February 2007) and OpenDocument 1.2 (29 September 2011). The file formats are in fact ZIP compression files within which XML files and any additions such as images have been collected. The free Apache OpenOffice software uses OpenDocument formats as standard formats. Outside of this package, OpenDocuments enjoy good support. Microsoft Office has supported OpenOffice formats since version 2007, although problems may occur with specific properties of the OpenDocuments. In many countries, including the Netherlands, the use of open source software and OpenDocuments has been set as standard for making government documentation accessible. OpenDocument formats are suitable for archiving, accessibility and reusability in the long term. The OpenDocument format for text documents is OpenDocument Text (.odt). ODT is a preferred format under the Text documents file type.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RACWIZCVgoa5kBIWp-HrL0BJ3Q9olrJrzS71yb4zWR2Cs/ODT>

2.b.1.y.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.y.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.z.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Structured Query Language (SQL)

Many DBMSs support the ISO-standardized version of Structured Query Language (SQL): a language for querying and updating relational databases. Together with the Data Definition Language, used to define and modify schemas, the contents of a database can be stored as a collection of schema and data statements. The language rarely changes, but the various modifications and additions may change along with software updates. If extensions are used, the documentation must show which SQL version is used. It is possible to refer to non-existent and / or external data in SQL, without invalidating the file. If SQL is used for exchanging data, any external references must therefore be supplied, or each reference must be replaced by the data referred to. SQL is a preferred format for file type Databases.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAfnkVgFx4KvHXuRbgksYKDBeom0bkZCILbVHsbqubWVg/SQL>

2.b.1.z.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.z.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.aa.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SIARD (Software Independent Archiving of Relational Databases)

For relational databases, SIARD is seen as a suitable and sustainable format. SIARD (Software Independent Archiving of Relational Databases) is intended for archiving relational databases in a way that is as independent of the original DBMS as possible. This format takes into account all the significant characteristics of databases. SIARD is an open, freely available format, based on clear text formats: Unicode, XML, SQL (1999). This makes it accessible for various tools. SIARD is a relatively young format, see SIARD_Suite. SIARD is a preferred format for file type Databases.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA62Ag2gp8ibx5doWpz05qhVFB1psRpIB1PVggHiBTo3g/SIARD>

2.b.1.aa.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.aa.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ab.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine)

DICOM stands for Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine. It is a communication standard for dealing with medical information generated by medical equipment, such as scanners. DICOM has been developed by the Medical Imaging and Technology Alliance (MITA). Before the communication standard existed, information was stored in various file formats associated with the software of a specific medical device. DICOM has put an end to this. DICOM is widely used and is the standard within medical digital image processing. Both doctors and medical imaging research groups use the DICOM file format for their research. In the standard, various types of images are supported for different medical applications, both still images and moving images. DICOM supports commonly used compression standards, such as JPEG and JPEG2000, or MPEG-2 for video images. The copyright on the standard is held by the American National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA). DICOM viewing software can be divided into two groups: (1) "proprietary" viewers that are part of the (medical) recording systems and (2) DICOM viewing software for PCs. Non-proprietary viewers that are available for free are DicomWorks, Osiris and IrfanView (a widely used all-format viewer). Adobe has developed a plugin for Photoshop that makes it possible to view or export DICOM images and "header" (= metadata) information to other formats. The IrfanView program is also capable of extracting images and / or animations (sequence of images) from DICOM files. DICOM files are a preferred format, due to their open specification and adoption as standard within the medical world. In certain circumstances it may be useful to save a single DICOM file from the entire dataset as .jpeg / tiff (the image) and .txt file (the header). This is due to the fact that few people outside the medical world have experience with DICOM. This way you can easily view one file from the dataset, without having to use an open DICOM viewer. As datasets containing DICOM files tend to be relatively large, we advise you to contact a DANS data manager before depositing these files. We are happy to advise you on the best way to deliver data and store it in the dataset for user-friendly purposes DICOM is a preferred format for file type Images (raster).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAS_b4iajRw-ODDffV_7eH1teblweoENfKhI4TiGZBkcw/DICOM

2.b.1.ab.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ab.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ac.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

JASP

JASP is a free platform-independent statistical software package with a graphical user interface. It is an open source alternative for proprietary software like SPSS, and is being developed by the University of Amsterdam. In JASP, you have the option to export data in formats which can be easily read into other applications such as .csv. Results of analyses are being exported in .html format. These formats have been added to our preferred formats within the file type of Statistical data.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAJlpwFjgNvyXuo7Ptj9rt12PYTAwwf1VYnoWpy4PJGKM/JASP>

2.b.1.ac.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ac.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ad.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

SVG (Scalable Vector Graphics)

SVG stands for “Scalable Vector Graphics”. It is a robust, XML-based format for statistical and dynamic vector images. SVG is an open standard and is well supported by various applications. SVG vector images can be opened in web browsers such as Firefox, Safari, Google Chrome, Microsoft Edge and Explorer. For further processing, vector image applications such as Adobe Illustrator or Inkscape can be used. Inkscape is free to download from the website and works on Windows, Mac OS X and Linux. All common Vector Image formats (EPS, AI, WMF, CDR) can be opened in Inkscape and Adobe Illustrator and converted to SVG. SVG is a preferred format for file type Images (vector) and for file type Computer Aided Design (CAD).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA95j1PLDXAKLilu-cuCZ9mJuH1iQTAPn61uBEVTHdzqU/SVG>

2.b.1.ad.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ad.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ae.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

BWF (Broadcast Wave Format)

The Broadcast Wave Format (BWF) is an open standard that is widely recommended as the archival master for audio preservation. It consists of uncompressed audio. It is an extension of the WAV format, since it may contain metadata which describes the format of the audio data and the encoding method, and carries a sample-accurate time stamp that can be used to place related files in the proper sequence. BWF can wrap either MPEG or LPCM encoding, although for long-term preservation the use of LPCM is preferred. BWF is a DANS preferred container format for Audio.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAXBk6Z_MLg87DiUe2rG8-K2ev8CiBDnmMGPXg--OiALY/BWF

2.b.1.ae.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ae.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.af.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

MXF (Material Exchange Format)

Material Exchange Format (MXF) is an open wrapper format developed by the Society of Motion Picture and Television Engineers. It supports a number of different bitstreams encoded with any of a variety of codecs, together with a metadata wrapper that describes the material contained within the MXF file. The wrapper is relatively transparent although the structure of an MXF file can be complex. Since invention of this format, there is an ever-increasing interest and adoption of MXF. It is emerging as a standard for professional digital video and audio media. For example,

the Library of Congress National Audio-Visual Conservation Center produces a form of MXF as archival masters as they reformat their older videotapes. MXF is a DANS preferred container format for audio and video.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA3jjLYXiibLw1e-IIZGBZTWLci-P8s85hMXkbyLhQu3E/MXF>

2.b.1.af.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.af.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ag.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Matroska Multimedia Container

The Matroska Multimedia Container is an open source, open standard multimedia container, that can wrap an unlimited number of audio, video, metadata and/or subtitle-files. Matroska Audio supports a large number of codecs. It has a very large userbase and is the basis for WebM media in HTML5/browsers. Most platforms offer native support for this format. Adoption of the file format is expected to further increase thanks to several outcomes of the PREFORMA project, including the Media Conch toolset, an implementation checker for Matroska. Matroska file extensions are .mkv for video (with subtitles and audio), .mka for audio-only files, and .mks for subtitles only. Matroska is a DANS preferred container format for audio and video.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAjuTONJRQPLaabYTvttWUxyVK7gSYtzJMqne9gxjVJlg/Matroska>

2.b.1.ag.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ag.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ah.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

FLAC (Free Lossless Audio Codec)

Free Lossless Audio Codec (FLAC) is an open format highly suitable for transcoding without quality loss (lossless compression). The FLAC specification includes a wrapper for FLAC bitstreams plus the lossless compression codec itself. FLAC can be used as a dissemination/delivery format, but is also a suitable format for the archival storage of audio streams. Adoption is moderate. FLAC is a DANS preferred format for audio, because of its lossless compression of digital audio, but adoption is moderate.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAPmdUqh0sYQLNSX7gC8Jod8ilhTV-wGj41tRq3x2bbc8/FLAC>

2.b.1.ah.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ah.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ai.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OPUS

OPUS is a codec for Audio formats.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RA2pB_w2_7Q-C16DzjRzIL265-qqw3BuqyM_8M4KpUZg/OPUS

2.b.1.ai.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ai.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.aj.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

AutoCAD DXF version R12 (ASCII)

The developer Autodesk, with the main software AutoCAD, is a market leader in the field of CAD. The AutoCAD formats DXF and DWG are used extensively. No open formats have been developed for the exchange of CAD formats. DXF is specifically designed to facilitate data interoperability between AutoCAD and other programs and is therefore well supported by other CAD applications. DXF version R12 (ASCII) appears to be best supported for successful and correct import into other applications. A major problem with the use of DXF is the development of the DWG format. DWG now offers possibilities for which not all properties can be stored in DXF. If export to DXF R12 (ASCII) does not lead to information loss, this version of the DXF format is considered the best option for preserving AutoCAD formats in a relatively open, widely supported format. A conversion from DWG to DXF must be carefully checked for completeness. If elements of the DWG cannot be stored in the DXF, an export to a more recent version of DXF is acceptable. If conversion is not possible without loss of information, the DWG must be retained. DXF version R12 (ASCII) is a preferred format for file type Computer Aided Design (CAD).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA6w0wNtOB509xKUVS541q3xUXScejIFJ61s0McGUqf0g/AutoCAD-DXF>

2.b.1.aj.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.aj.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ak.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

GML

GML is the XML standard for geographic data, designed by the Open Geospatial Consortium. Since August 2007, GML has been adopted as the ISO standard ISO 19136. Support for GML was initially limited but has since increased significantly, now GIS applications can be expected to be able to correctly import GML data. GML is a preferred format for file type GIS. Read more about GIS.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAiTGrsSH2uHsTmV1u4ThMzt6XDtmTatHLs17Wfg2DT5Y/GML>

2.b.1.ak.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ak.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.al.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

MIF/MID (Mapinfo Interchange Format)

The "MapInfo Interchange Format" .mif, usually associated with the .mid file, is the export format of the MapInfo software, designed for GIS interoperability. It is a clear, well documented, well

supported and stable ASCII text file. It can be expected from GIS applications that they can correctly import MIF/MID data and that map layers in the application's own format can be exported to MIF/MID. MIF/MID is a preferred format for file type GIS.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAogiFSBeFg4b0ChsFNQl6GM3SPGrObK7ajFu4nj0HGbl/MIF-MID>

2.b.1.al.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.al.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.am.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

GeoTIFF

GeoTIFF is a metadata standard for adding georeference to a TIFF image. This metadata is included in the TIFF file itself. GeoTIFF is an extension of TIFF, an open format in the public domain. The format is supported by various commonly used GIS applications. GeoTIFF is a preferred format for file type Images (georeference).

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAIRt8fgFA8f-nPVRgNfiQJeKDDYBLwvdb4VOmaGxYsgM/GeoTIFF>

2.b.1.am.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.am.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.an.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ASCII GRID

It is advisable to convert Grid files to ASCII text as much as possible. It can be expected from GIS applications that they can correctly import ASCII grid files. ASCII GRID is a preferred format for file type raster grid.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAPJb_oNQ97DD722_Vuc6v8awjgw0fMI0Y8Yce7GqbzTA/ASCII-GRID

2.b.1.an.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.an.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ao.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

WaveFront Object

WaveFront Object is a very widely supported open file format for the representation of 3D geometry. The file contains a clear, simple structure in which the spatial positions of each point of the object and texture coordinates are written. The .obj file can be supplied as an ASCII text file or as a binary format. ASCII OBJ is preferred for accessibility and archiving in the long term. In addition to the .obj file, material / texture information can be stored in an .mtl file. The texture itself is saved separately as an image. Read more about raster images: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/images-raster/>. OBJ does not store information about animations. WaveFront Object is a preferred format for file type 3D.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RApO9TYo2mU1pEHJ3I_UISko8ZuKg92rBSh5xvGzqbyn4/WaveFront

2.b.1.ao.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ao.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ap.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Polygon File Format (PLY)

PLY is also known as the Stanford Triangle Format. It is a WaveFront Object-inspired format with the option of extensions describing additional features of a 3D model, including color and transparency. The .ply file can be supplied as an ASCII text file or as a binary format. ASCII PLY is preferred for accessibility and archiving in the long term. Not every software supports all extensions of the Polygon file format: it is possible that the data is not completely read, depending on the software used. That is why it is especially important with PLY that it is well documented which information the data contains. Polygon file format is a preferred format for file type 3D.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RATHm_eG4G3JKYxz2bCp230ZXHimh3z8CBdFZds_5j9ko/Polygon-file-format

2.b.1.ap.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ap.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.aq.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

X3D File Format

The X3D format is managed by the non-profit organization Web3D Consortium. It is an XML-based ISO standard set up with the aim of becoming the 3D standard for the web. In addition to a few 3D models, the format is also suitable for storing complex 3D data such as virtual reality. X3D contains fairly extensive support for the storage of graphic elements. X3D is a preferred format for file type 3D.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RA-2EV3Q9qzHF1VyV_aGHU9_vTyltiA1EwO2OCCI9j-VQ/X3D

2.b.1.aq.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.aq.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.ar.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

glTF 2.0 File Format

The Graphics Language Transmission Format was designed as an interoperable format for loading scenes and models created with 3D tools, in modern applications. The glTF format is a JSON-based text format and is accompanied by binary data (.bin) for geometry, animations, and other associated data; and raster images (.jpg; .png) for textures. There are two versions of glTF: glTF 1.0, first released in October 2015; and glTF 2.0, released in June 2017. Version 2.0 is a significant upgrade from version 1.0 and is aimed at better support from applications. With the increasing adoption of version 2.0, version 1.0 seems to have become obsolete. glb is the extension for binary glTF: a container format that collects the glTF and its associated data into a single file. Binary glTF was introduced as an extension for glTF 1.0 and was incorporated in the glTF 2.0 specification.

glTF is being developed in an open project by the non-profit organization Khronos Group. glTF 2.0 is a preferred format for file type 3D. glb is a preferred format for file type 3D on the condition that it is based on glTF 2.0. glTF 1.0 and glb based on glTF 1.0 are non-preferred formats for file type 3D.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RA9H_uwgeeV6r_FGwXg6p-Fr6uemQLGzoTApRZCuIRVDU/glTF

2.b.1.ar.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.ar.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.as.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

COLLADA File Format

COLLADA is an open-source XML format for storing interactive 3D applications. It was designed by Sony in collaboration with various large graphic design organizations. Today, COLLADA is managed by the non-profit organization Khronos Group. COLLADA .dae has been adopted by ISO as a publicly available specification. COLLADA is supported by popular software packages such as (GIS application) ArcGIS, (CAD application) Autodesk Infrastructure Modeller, Google Earth v1.4, Mac OS X 10.6 Preview. COLLADA supports various graphic 3D elements. It is intended as an intermediate format: to redirect 3D information in parts to other software. However, the file specification of COLLADA is not very strict, which means that interoperability between COLLADA exports from different software can cause problems. Although DANS marked COLLADA as a preferred format, X3D is preferred if 3D data can be supplied in X3D. COLLADA is a preferred format for file type 3D.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RA7voCvBYsQaxP-xbcqIFT0HKB7C1i_Yyvble17VTztLQ/COLLADA

2.b.1.as.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.as.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.at.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

IFC (Industry Foundation Classes)

Industry Foundation Classes (.ifc) is an open, XML-based data model for the exchange of building information model data: data about buildings, construction and maintenance. It can describe all

kinds of details of building structures. It was also designed to support CAD data. Various software packages support IFC, and there are also several free viewers available. IFC is a preferred format for file types 3D and CAD.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RA2i47VTPHjweiAlwmqYI_4ebAaTMbuXp7avvJ7Og2PpU/IFC

2.b.1.at.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.at.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.au.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

TriG

TriG is a plain text serialization format designed for storing RDF datasets containing multiple graphs within a single file. It's a compact and readable alternative to other XML-based syntaxes. It's an extension of the Turtle syntax, adding functionality to allow graph separation, which is useful for representing datasets with different contexts or versions. TriG has been standardized

by the W3C.

TriG is a preferred serialization for RDF data.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAQwJongKgkOjPpaegHrg4ImAlt1aj4FbKKGH-i1XKK7c/TriG>

2.b.1.au.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.au.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.av.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

N-Triples format

N-Triples is a format for storing and transmitting data. It is a line-based, plain text serialisation format for RDF (Resource Description Framework) graphs, and a subset of the Turtle (Terse RDF Triple Language) format.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAmB_YG3TWTE-G51xryPusqyWyh2VxDrwF4PKNWMN_tDc#NTriples

2.b.1.av.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.av.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Supporting Declaration I1 Datasets: What FAIR representation services do you use to create FAIR data?

A transformation service that converts non-FAIR data into a FAIR representation using machine-readable knowledge representation languages.

- ✓ a. Supporting Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

3.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4

Declaration I2 Metadata: What structured vocabulary do you use to annotate your metadata records?

In Principle I2 we referred to “vocabularies” as the methods that unambiguously represent concepts that exist in a given domain. The use of shared, and formally structured (principle I1), sets of terms is an essential part of FAIR. Terminology systems, including flat “vocabularies”, hierarchical “thesauri” and more granular specifications of knowledge such as data models and consistently structured ontologies, play an important role in community standards. However, the vocabularies used for metadata or data also need to be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable in their own right so that users (including machines) can fully understand the meaning of the terms used in the metadata. This principle has been criticized as “circular” but as has been made clear earlier in the Digital Intelligence article, the simple use of a “label” (e.g. “temperature”) is insufficient to enable a machine to understand both the intent of that label (Body temperature? Melting temperature?) and the contexts within which it can be properly linked – same-with-same – to other similarly-labeled data. I2, therefore, requires that the vocabulary terms used in the knowledge representation language (principle I1) can be sufficiently distinguished, by a machine, to resolve to the intended defined meaning and thus ensure detection and prevention of “false agreements” as well as “false disagreements” on exact meaning of the identifier

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “structured vocabulary” which is a specification of uniquely identified and unambiguous concepts with their definitions represented using web standards.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

NARCIS Classification of Scientific Disciplines

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAkOIKhrmVKOIMKHo9equNII3NHZBgrT-j0Z6ctI59RUE/NARCIS-Classification>

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ This controlled vocabulary has been used by DANS to classify audiences of the datasets.

4.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ISO 639-2:1998

ISO 639-2:1998 provides two sets of three-letter alphabetic codes for the representation of names of languages, one for terminology applications and the other for bibliographic applications. The code sets are the same except for twenty-five languages that have variant language codes because of the criteria used for formulating them. The language codes were devised originally for use by libraries, information services, and publishers to indicate language in the exchange of information, especially in computerized systems. ISO 639-2 represents all languages contained in ISO 639-1 and in addition any other language as well as language groups as they may be coded for special purposes when more specificity in coding is needed. The languages listed in ISO 639-1 are a subset of the languages listed in ISO 639-2; every language

code in the two-letter code set has a corresponding language code in the alpha-3 list, but not necessarily vice versa.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAbEYoehliTuZc_wi39KNK5HuQ4oulFpRoAFYE5sym4s#ISO_639-2_1998

4.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use a standard list of languages to document the language used in the data or metadata.

4.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ISO 3166-1:2013 Codes for the representation of names of countries and their subdivisions

- Part 1: Country codes

ISO 3166-1:2013 is intended for use in any application requiring the expression of current country names in coded form. It also includes basic guidelines for its implementation and maintenance.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAKy68K-ubbaV8BKrbYyJQ1NYKcCkvQPpgrQ7rdWbvjRU#ISO_3166

4.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use a standard list of countries in our spatial coverage field to document information about a country the data or metadata relates to.

4.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DDI Controlled Vocabularies

The Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) Controlled Vocabularies Group (CVG) has created a set of controlled vocabularies (CVs) that can be used with DDI as well as for other purposes and applications. The DDI CVs are used to aid in the description and documentation of data in the social science research community. The published DDI-CVs work with both versions of the DDI specification (DDI-L and DDI-C).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAZVaY2uNntlyJJVo_f43W9csVA_TohoawN9ZzM0SECs#DDI-Controlled-Vocabularies

4.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ c. Is planned to be used in the future

4.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ These vocabularies are recommended by the Consortium for European Social Science Data Archives.

4.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

AAT | Art and Architecture thesaurus

The Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) is a structured vocabulary for describing and indexing the visual arts and architecture.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAdx63gjTah4GBIHOn4csAJ5g7njVLvlbyJdGKR-72k#AAT>

4.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

European Language Social Science Thesaurus | ELSST

The European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) is a broad-based, multilingual thesaurus for the social sciences. It is owned and published by the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) and its national Service Providers. The thesaurus consists of over 3,300 concepts and covers the core social science disciplines: politics, sociology, economics, education, law, crime, demography, health, employment, information, communication technology, and environmental science. ELSST is used for data discovery within CESSDA and facilitates access to data resources across Europe, independent of domain, resource, language, or vocabulary.

ELSST is currently available in 16 languages: Danish, Dutch, Czech, English, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Icelandic, Lithuanian, Norwegian, Romanian, Slovenian, Spanish, and Swedish

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.acd824>

4.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Geonames Ontology

The GeoNames geographical database contains over 25 million geographical names and consists of over 12 million unique features whereof 4.8 million populated places and 16 million alternate names.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAyCOlaBc8A3weNZBI_xBq9hirbtoJgR6V1VqeoSMef5E/Geonames-ontology

4.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✔ c. Is planned to be used in the future

4.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4.b.1.h.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Research Organization Registry ID Schema | ROR ID

The Research Organization Registry (ROR) ID schema is the specification of the identifier for institutions in ROR. ROR is a global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research organizations. ROR makes it easy for anyone or any system to disambiguate institution names and connect research organizations to researchers and research outputs.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.f73143>

4.b.1.h.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.h.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ ROR identifiers can be used to refer to an organization.

4.b.1.i.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DANS Identifiers Type

Controlled vocabulary IdentifierType used in the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAcLZ9PEH8OSk4VAOaL97r5JbEjg0-R6IKrBu792qW4j4/DANS_Identifiers_Type

4.b.1.i.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.i.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use a vocabulary of common identifiers to select identifier types from <https://doi.org/10.34894/NQZ4JG>

4.b.1.j.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DANS Contributor

Vontrolled vocabulary Contributor Type used in the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). The DANS Data Station SSH is a trustworthy digital repository for research data in the SSH domain offered by DANS in the Netherlands. <https://ssh.datastations.nl/> In the DANS Data Station SSH various vocabularies are used. This dataset provides information about the Contributor Type vocabulary. It lists the elements a user can choose from as well as the source from which the vocabulary term was selected (if applicable).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAKR0Gixg5m50bBIDAOriDQ_IQjEoOkrV58wQagAynJ9k/DANS_Contributor

4.b.1.j.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.j.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use a vocabulary based on DataCite elements to describe a contributor <https://doi.org/10.34894/XWUMPJ>

4.b.1.k.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DANS Personal Data

Controlled vocabulary Personal Data used in the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). The DANS Data Station SSH is a trustworthy digital repository for research data in the SSH domain offered by DANS in the Netherlands. <https://ssh.datastations.nl/> In the DANS Data Station SSH various vocabularies are used. This dataset provides information about the Personal Data vocabulary. It lists the elements a user can choose from as well as the source from which the vocabulary term was selected (if applicable).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAZNyng3oiswAFogvdJm43DLR4WqSKLONHgZjDU5QpcO4/DANS_Personal_Data

4.b.1.k.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.k.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use a vocabulary to indicate if personal data is present in a dataset <https://doi.org/10.34894/OWIVA2>

4.b.1.l.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DANS Relations

Controlled vocabulary Relation used in the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). The DANS Data Station SSH is a trustworthy digital repository for research data in the SSH domain offered by DANS in the Netherlands. <https://ssh.datastations.nl/> In the DANS Data Station SSH various vocabularies are used. This dataset provides information about the Relation vocabulary. It lists the elements a user can choose from as well as the source from which the vocabulary term was selected (if applicable).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAPcyewMaWB7DqjXcstpGsT3uT4zrOlaUNPFNDIGPmQxE/DANS_Relations

4.b.1.l.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.l.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use a controlled list of terms from Dublin Core and DataCite to refer to the type of relation or related materials.

4.b.1.m.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CESSDA Topic Classification

CESSDA Topic Classification contains a typology of main themes or subjects of data.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAGxugwVCKErDw8TCtPpRiTcygzWXxKRwMEJc4jUyYw-#CESSDATC>

4.b.1.m.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.m.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4.b.1.n.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Dataverse Subject Terms

Controlled vocabulary Subject Terms used in the DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). In the DANS Data Station SSH various vocabularies are used. This dataset provides information about the Subject vocabulary. It lists the elements a user can choose from as well as the source from which the vocabulary term was selected (if applicable).

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RArfKB8xbl1oAq18nFH8ivT-PTq11qx4ZGKkplj29X8ZI/Dataverse_Subject

4.b.1.n.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.n.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

5

Declaration I2 Datasets: What structured vocabulary do you use to encode your datasets

In Principle I2 we referred to “vocabularies” as the methods that unambiguously represent concepts that exist in a given domain. The use of shared, and formally structured (principle I1), sets of terms is an essential part of FAIR. Terminology systems, including flat “vocabularies”, hierarchical “thesauri” and more granular specifications of knowledge such as data models and consistently structured ontologies, play an important role in community standards. However, the vocabularies used for metadata or data also need to be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable in their own right so that users (including machines) can fully understand the meaning of the terms used in the metadata. This principle has been criticized as “circular” but as has been made clear earlier in the Digital Intelligence article, the simple use of a “label” (e.g. “temperature”) is insufficient to enable a machine to understand both the intent of that label (Body temperature? Melting temperature?) and the contexts within which it can be properly linked – same-with-same – to other similarly-labeled data. I2, therefore, requires that the vocabulary terms used in the knowledge representation language (principle I1) can be sufficiently distinguished, by a machine, to resolve to the intended defined meaning and thus ensure detection and prevention of “false agreements” as well as “false disagreements” on exact meaning of the identifier

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “structured vocabulary” which is a specification of uniquely identified and unambiguous concepts with their definitions represented using web standards.

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

5.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

6

Supporting Declaration I2: What editor do you use to create vocabularies?

An editor is a service that provides user-friendly interface for easy editing of metadata, vocabularies and crosswalks.

✓ a. Supporting Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

6.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

7

Declaration I3 Metadata: What semantic model do you use for your metadata records?

An important aspect of the I in FAIR is that data or metadata, generally speaking, does not exist in a silo – we must do what is necessary to ensure that the knowledge representing a resource is connected to that of other resources to create a meaningfully interlinked network of data and services. A “qualified reference” is a reference to another resource (i.e., referencing that external resource's persistent identifier), in which the nature of the relationship is also clearly specified. For instance, when multiple versions of a metadata file are available, it may be useful to provide links to prior or next versions using a named relation such as “prior version” or “next version” (using an appropriate community standard relationship that itself conforms to the FAIR principles). In the case of data, imagine a dataset that specifies the population of cities around the world. To be FAIR with respect to principle I3, the data could contain links to a resource containing city data (e.g., <https://www.wikidata.org/> D. Vrandečić . Wikidata: A new platform for collaborative data collection. In: Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on World Wide Web, 2012, pp. 1063–1064. 10.1145/2187980.2188242), geographical and geospatial data, or other related domain resources that are generated by that city, so long as they are properly qualified references using meaningful, clearly-interpretable relationships. It is also important to note that many different metadata files (containers) being FAIR digital resources in themselves, can be pointing to the same “target” object (a data set or a workflow for instance). For instance a FAIR Digital Object constructed as a nanopublication can have intrinsic metadata (“what is this”) and how was it created (provenance type metadata) as well as “secondary” metadata that are for instance created (separately and later in time) by reusers of a particular digital resource. These could all be metadata containers essentially describing the same digital resource from different perspectives. This principle therefore also relates to the good practice to clearly distinguish between metadata (files/containers) and the resources they describe.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “semantic model” which is a specification that defines qualified relations between entities describing data or other digital objects using structured vocabularies. A semantic model can be a conceptual model expressed as an ontology or as a metadata scheme that reuses terms from FAIR vocabularies.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

7.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

7.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DANS Data Station SSH Metadata Template

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAFsywMXu5ZwNKhtjyK_6PpRt3XdRQF4LHlle2WfCLBY/DANS-Datastation-SSH-MD-Template

7.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

7.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- We have a set of metadata elements and linked vocabularies based on existing standards (DataCite, CEESDA, DDI) using Dataverse technology as basis for the repository.

Declaration I3 Datasets: What semantic model do you use for your datasets?

An important aspect of the I in FAIR is that data or metadata, generally speaking, does not exist in a silo – we must do what is necessary to ensure that the knowledge representing a resource is connected to that of other resources to create a meaningfully interlinked network of data and services. A “qualified reference” is a reference to another resource (i.e., referencing that external resource's persistent identifier), in which the nature of the relationship is also clearly specified. For instance, when multiple versions of a metadata file are available, it may be useful to provide links to prior or next versions using a named relation such as “prior version” or “next version” (using an appropriate community standard relationship that itself conforms to the FAIR principles). In the case of data, imagine a dataset that specifies the population of cities around the world. To be FAIR with respect to principle I3, the data could contain links to a resource containing city data (e.g., <https://www.wikidata.org/> D. Vrandečić . Wikidata: A new platform for collaborative data collection. In: Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on World Wide Web, 2012, pp. 1063–1064. 10.1145/2187980.2188242), geographical and geospatial data, or other related domain resources that are generated by that city, so long as they are properly qualified references using meaningful, clearly-interpretable relationships. It is also important to note that many different metadata files (containers) being FAIR digital resources in themselves, can be pointing to the same “target” object (a data set or a workflow for instance). For instance a FAIR Digital Object constructed as a nanopublication can have intrinsic metadata (“what is this”) and how was it created (provenance type metadata) as well as “secondary” metadata that are for instance created (separately and later in time) by reusers of a particular digital resource. These could all be metadata containers essentially describing the same digital resource from different perspectives. This principle therefore also relates to the good practice to clearly distinguish between metadata (files/containers) and the resources they describe.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “semantic model” which is a specification that defines qualified relations between entities describing data or other digital objects using structured vocabularies. A semantic model can be a conceptual model expressed as an ontology or as a metadata scheme that reuses terms from FAIR vocabularies.

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

8.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

Supporting Declaration I3: What crosswalks do you use to link different schemas?

A crosswalk is a set of rules that defines how (meta)data elements or attributes (i.e., slots) from one schema or format can be aligned and mapped to (meta)data elements or attributes in another schema or format that share the same constraints and thus share the same semantic role.

✓ b. Supporting Declaration: FAIR Supporting Resource(s)**9.b.1****List the FAIR Supporting Resource(s)****Answers****9.b.1.a.1****Select the FAIR Supporting Resource****Dataverse Metadata Crosswalk**

Dataverse software provides an export to various metadata formats and performs the mapping between the Dataverse fields and these exports. An overview of the Datavers Crosswalk can be found at: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1VAhZ83hKURX_4T-bOkn7XCb9h62Gr2gcJl1fWe4RI4c/ <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/admin/metadataexport.html>

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAXO8MLavK9-luKTOOaylSBCCyENGB-6CaKnLp271Y_bw/Dataverse_Metadata_Crosswalk

9.b.1.a.2**This implementation choice is:**

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community**

9.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ Dataverse software provides an export to various metadata formats and performs the mapping between the Dataverse fields and these exports.

10

Supporting Declaration I3: What editor do you use create crosswalks?

An editor is a service that provides user-friendly interface for easy editing of metadata, vocabularies and crosswalks.

- ✓ a. Supporting Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

10.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

VI. Declarations for Reusability

At first glance, principle R1 appears very similar to principle F2. However, the rationale behind principle F2 is to enable effective attribute-based search and query (findability), while the focus of R1 is to enable machines and humans to assess if the discovered resource is appropriate for intended reuse, given a specific task. For example, not all gene expression data for a given locus are relevant to a study of the effects of heat stress. While irrelevant data may be discovered by the agent's initial search (principle F2) for expression data about a given gene, here we address the ability to assess and filter the discovered data based on suitability-for-purpose. This reiterates the need for good data stewards to consider not only high-level metadata facets, that will assist in generic search, but also to consider more detailed metadata that will provide much more "operational" instructions for re-use. In this setting, a wide variety of factors may be needed to determine whether a resource is suitable for inclusion in an analysis, and how to adequately process it. The term "plurality" is used to indicate that the metadata author should be as generous as possible, not narrowly presuming who the secondary consumers might be, and therefore provide as much metadata as possible to support the widest variety of use-cases and agent needs. The sub-principles R1.1, R1.2 and R1.3 further define some critical types of attributes that contribute to R1.

Summary

Answered (current phase)	62 / 62	
Answered	66 / 89	

Questions

1

Declaration R1.1 Metadata: Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?

Digital resources and their metadata must always, without exception, include a license that describes under which conditions the resource can be used, even if that is “unconditional”. By default, resources cannot be legally used without this clarity. Note also that a license that cannot be found by an agent, is effectively the same as no license at all. Furthermore, the license may be different for a data resource and the metadata that describes it, which has implications for the indexing of metadata v.v. findability. It also reiterates the need to separate and permalink data and metadata. This is a clear public domain statement, an equivalent such as terms of use or computer protocol to digitally facilitate an operation (for instance a smart contract). Thus, the absence of a license does not indicate “open”, but rather creates legal uncertainty that will deter (in fact, in many cases legally prevent) reuse. Note also that the combination of resources with permissive as well as more restrictive license conditions may lead to adverse effects, and ultimately preclude the use of the combined resources for particular purposes. In order to facilitate reuse, the license chosen should be as open as possible.(see additional criteria GFF)

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “data usage license” which is a document that describes the conditions under which a digital object can be legally used.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC0 1.0 | CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication

You can copy, modify, distribute and perform the work, even for commercial purposes, all without asking permission.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAq55jS4TCF-u0HLARDjWevzMv8k-NY7737bSjVzRAY2w#CC0-1.0>

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration R1.1 Datasets: Which usage license do you use for your datasets?

Digital resources and their metadata must always, without exception, include a license that describes under which conditions the resource can be used, even if that is “unconditional”. By default, resources cannot be legally used without this clarity. Note also that a license that cannot be found by an agent, is effectively the same as no license at all. Furthermore, the license may be different for a data resource and the metadata that describes it, which has implications for the indexing of metadata v.v. findability. It also reiterates the need to separate and permalink data and metadata. This is a clear public domain statement, an equivalent such as terms of use or computer protocol to digitally facilitate an operation (for instance a smart contract). Thus, the absence of a license does not indicate “open”, but rather creates legal uncertainty that will deter (in fact, in many cases legally prevent) reuse. Note also that the combination of resources with permissive as well as more restrictive license conditions may lead to adverse effects, and ultimately preclude the use of the combined resources for particular purposes. In order to facilitate reuse, the license chosen should be as open as possible.(see additional criteria GFF)

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “data usage license” which is a document that describes the conditions under which a digital object can be legally used.

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC0 1.0 | CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication

You can copy, modify, distribute and perform the work, even for commercial purposes, all without asking permission.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAq55jS4TCF-u0HLARDjWevzMv8k-NY7737bSjVzRAY2w#CC0-1.0>

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC BY 4.0 | Attribution 4.0 International

Using this licence you are free to share and adapt the resource but you must give appropriate credit.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc7l1O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DANS License

The DANS licence sets out the conditions for using datasets which are published under Restricted access Anyone to whom DANS, on behalf of the holder of the rights to the dataset, makes one or more files of a dataset available (hereinafter referred to as the User), agrees to the following conditions. Acceptance of the conditions establishes an agreement between DANS and the User.

1. Responsible use The User will act in accordance with the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, the GDPR and other applicable laws and regulations.

2. Citing the dataset The User will always cite the dataset in the research results they publish, in whatever form, when it has been used in the research. This source reference will at least consist of:
 3. The names and/or organisations of the producers of the dataset;
 4. The year in which the dataset was produced;
 5. The title of the dataset;
 6. The name of organisation managing the archive in which the dataset is stored: DANS;
 7. The persistent identifier of the dataset as a full URL.
8. Distribution or disclosure of the dataset The User shall respect all intellectual property rights to the dataset, such as copyrights, database and/or neighbouring rights. For distribution or disclosure of the entire dataset or of substantial parts thereof, the User must first request permission from the holder of the rights to the dataset. This is the person(s) and/or institution(s) listed in the "Rights holder" metadata field of the dataset. If no holder is listed in this field, the User must contact the person(s) and/or organisation of the person(s) who produced the dataset.
9. Statement when distributing or disclosing the dataset When distributing or disclosing the entire dataset or substantial parts of it, in the manner described in Article 2 of this DANS Licence and with the permission of the rights holder, the User shall, in addition to the acknowledgement referred to in Article 2, declare at all times:
 10. the name of the dataset rights holder;
 11. that this rights holder has granted permission for the distribution;
 12. that further distribution by third parties is not permitted without the consent of the dataset rights holder.
13. Publications The User will inform DANS of the publications for which the dataset has been used. In this context, publications are defined as publications with an internationally recognized standard identification number, such as ISBN, ISSN or DOI. If a publication is available on the internet, the User will pass on the URL to DANS. If a publication is not available on the internet (via an URL), the User will pass on the source reference to DANS.
14. Personal data The User will always be responsible for the processing of personal data made available within the meaning of the GDPR and any other relevant privacy legislation, as well as for complying with any conditions set by the depositor.
15. Liability for content DANS shall in no way be liable for the contents or accompanying documentation of the dataset, including infringements of privacy rights within the meaning of the GDPR, unless in the event of intent or gross negligence on the part of DANS. The User is requested to inform DANS of any inaccuracies found as soon as possible after their discovery. Neither DANS nor the depositor provide any guarantee that a dataset made available will meet the research objectives of the User. Neither DANS nor the depositor are liable for conclusions based on the dataset.
16. Non-compliance with licence conditions
 - a. If the licence conditions are not complied with, the use of the dataset must immediately be discontinued upon DANS's first request. DANS reserves the right to inform the User's employer. In the event of unlawful use of personal data, DANS has the right to inform the Data Protection Authority as well. These measures are without prejudice to the authority of DANS to hold the User to account in court in the event of non-compliance or insufficient compliance with this licence.
 - b. If the licence conditions are not complied with, the User's access to datasets other than that of the rights holder will be suspended until the issue has been resolved in consultation with the User, their employer and the rights holder (where applicable).
 - c. The User will indemnify

DANS against all claims by third parties which are directly or indirectly related to the use of a dataset made available.

17. Compelling reasons For compelling reasons, such as, but not limited to, an infringement of other people's copyright or an infringement of the Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, DANS has the right to order the User to stop using the dataset.
18. Changes to the agreement DANS reserves the right to unilaterally change this agreement. In the event of substantial changes, DANS will inform the User, through DANS's repository or by other means, before the new conditions take effect, so that the User has the opportunity to become aware of the changes. If the User does not accept the changes, the User must stop using the dataset(s) and delete any downloaded files. By continuing to use the dataset(s) after the changes have taken effect, the User accepts the updated conditions.
19. Applicable law a. This licence is governed by Dutch law. b. Disputes that cannot be resolved amicably will be submitted to the competent court in the Amsterdam district.
20. See metadata [here](#)
21. See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAA6xLBbyYc4I7HOXF8Lck_bHyiezo9f1IN0OIYXI_2Dc/DANSLicence

2.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC BY SA 4.0 | Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International

Using this license you are free to share and adapt the resource but you must give appropriate credit.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RAEEcqbP_ghoZdqL-qsYp3YREEZMKuXb4t7xSGnlov8#CC-BY-SA-4.0

2.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC BY-NC 4.0 | Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International

This license allows reusers to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format for noncommercial purposes only, and only so long as attribution is given to the creator.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RANw_e-9CEfADSpQKbEVn5G7qu_jczqdJUNssOzYXEvfA#CC-BY-NC-4.0

2.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 | Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International

Using this license you are free to share and adapt this resource but you must give appropriate credit.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAsHps5X17EiVP-ByVsvlqn3rKwP64PFqjH1IWY4Pe5i4#CC-BY-NC-ND-4.0>

2.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 | Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International

Using this license you are free to share and adapt this resource but you must give appropriate credit.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAzULQmwy3wZ8laY-ZKZ3kXGmAihweBvKMU70RR638804#CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0>

2.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.h.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC BY-ND 4.0 | Attribution-NoDerivatives 4.0 International

Using this license you are free to share and adapt this resource but you must give appropriate credit.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RALxHDLNgvWuWjhWu2sdrfQB-W-v2uaHFbqlwR-xB6Cg0#CC-BY-ND-4.0>

2.b.1.h.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.h.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.i.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

BSD 2-Clause "Simplified" License

Redistribution and use in source and binary forms, with or without modification, are permitted provided that some conditions are met.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAeNjzwDJBAVwExEiGfRzc8C0RhKluTrZxDf5RTMRuAdw#BSD-2-Clause>

2.b.1.i.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.i.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.j.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

BSD 3-Clause "New" or "Revised" License

Redistribution and use in source and binary forms, with or without modification, are permitted provided that some conditions are met.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RAeB7rO4dbDI-oFz-G5oSe4Ih-7W9IRIZkVwG6p0AIP-E#BSD-3-Clause>

2.b.1.j.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.j.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.k.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

MIT License

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- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RA24ysQcpWDzK6wHANKG_3F1HiTbgOO4ULjYxjaXDi8C4#MIT

2.b.1.k.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.k.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.l.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Apache 2 Software License

The Apache License is a permissive free software license written by the Apache Software Foundation (ASF). The Apache License 2.0 attempts to forestall potential patent litigation.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RA8mzNIRc8TDNYkp0yMbGTlxqknBNpiflO4GvLRlzP-KY#Apache-2>

2.b.1.l.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.l.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.m.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CeCILL Free Software License Agreement v2.0

This Agreement is a Free Software license agreement that is the result of discussions between its authors in order to ensure compliance with the two main principles guiding its drafting: -firstly, compliance with the principles governing the distribution of Free Software: access to source code, broad rights granted to users, -secondly, the election of a governing law, French law, with which it is conformant, both as regards the law of torts and intellectual property law, and the protection that it offers to both authors and holders of the economic rights over software.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAgFydo0mJwKFM5NaCMjID-4JvujKFddPgP0fWM3r1AqY/CeCILL_V2

2.b.1.m.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.m.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.n.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

GPL-3.0-only | GNU General Public License v3.0 only

GNU General Public License v3.0 only

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RARdTFZT5FpZnrTATpLHkZk-AWbjY7XvBjzEbOI4ZqHn0#GPL-3.0-only>

2.b.1.n.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.n.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.o.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

LGPL-3.0-or-later | GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0 or later

GNU Lesser General Public License v3.0 or later

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: http://purl.org/np/RA4xRfS-19le_ysrtzf5ZgKwDXgwDlk8doZyJWEHj24A8#LGPL-3.0-or-later

2.b.1.o.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.o.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.p.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Mozilla Public License (MPL) v2.0

The MPL is a simple copyleft license. The MPL's "file-level" copyleft is designed to encourage contributors to share modifications they make to your code, while still allowing them to combine your code with code under other licenses (open or proprietary) with minimal restrictions.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAuw-zmWNj5rGb9rci9oiRBFFqvxMU-f-smbxsCGt80Yc/MPL-2.0>

2.b.1.p.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.p.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.q.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

TAPR Open Hardware License v1.0

Open Hardware is a thing - a physical artifact, either electrical or mechanical - whose design information is available to, and usable by, the public in a way that allows anyone to make, modify, distribute, and use that thing. In this preface, design information is called "documentation" and things created from it are called "products." The TAPR Open Hardware License ("OHL") agreement provides a legal framework for Open Hardware projects. It may be used for any kind of product, be it a hammer or a computer motherboard, and is TAPR's contribution to the community; anyone may use the OHL for their Open Hardware project.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RAiMZA5rI0T9Of9-2WQ6lzFlJmApbZse9mtxEoJOwA2w/TAPR-OHL-1.0>

2.b.1.q.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.q.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ TAPR-OHL-1.0 <https://tapr.org/the-tapr-open-hardware-license/>

2.b.1.r.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CERN Open Hardware Licence 1.1

The CERN Open Hardware Licence (OHL) v1.1 is a legal framework designed to facilitate the sharing and modification of hardware designs, similar to how open-source software licenses work. It allows for the use, copying, modification, and distribution of hardware designs and products based on those designs. Version 1.1, released in July 2011, built upon the initial version (1.0) by incorporating community feedback and aligning with open-source principles.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <https://w3id.org/np/RA29RBCgWlsBsLJWCMzfQzs1GZ3z24rlhEiV6WcOrjz4/CERN-OHL-1.1>

2.b.1.r.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.r.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.s.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

GPL-2.0-or-later | GNU General Public License v2.0 or later

GNU General Public License v2.0 or later

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: <http://purl.org/np/RArMUY5qtnXGv9tRwzCKrwRD6Xo7gMqNr59bZs9lboD6Q#GPL-2.0-or-later>

2.b.1.s.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.s.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.t.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CeCILL-B Free Software License Agreement

This Agreement is a Free Software license agreement that is the result of discussions between its authors in order to ensure compliance with the two main principles guiding its drafting: -firstly, compliance with the principles governing the distribution of Free Software: access to source code, broad rights granted to users, -secondly, the election of a governing law, French law, with which it is conformant, both as regards the law of torts and intellectual property law, and the protection that it offers to both authors and holders of the economic rights over software. The license is specifically crafted to be fully compatible with BSD-style licenses like BSD, X11, and MIT. This compatibility is achieved by allowing the distribution of modified code under any license, provided proper attribution is given. This is different from the GPL, which can restrict how modifications are licensed.

- See metadata [here](#)

- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAweAdNrCQ0y-uWTpBEFdJUvz2oh0OwsxeWM2-cZimiqQ/CeCILL_V2

2.b.1.t.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.t.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration R1.2 Metadata: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?

Detailed provenance includes facets such as how the resource was generated, why it was generated, by whom, under what conditions, using what starting-data or source-resource, using what funding/resources, who owns the data, who should be given credit, and any filters or cleansing processes that have been applied post-generation. Provenance information helps people and machines assess whether a resource meets their criteria for their intended reuse, and what data manipulation procedures may be necessary in order to reuse it appropriately.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “provenance model” which is a specification (schema) that defines metadata fields describing the origin and lineage of data or other digital objects. A prominent provenance model is PROV that can be used and implemented in metadata templates.

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Dataverse Support for Dataset Versions

Dataverse provides provenance facilities on dataset level and file level. A Dataverse installation accepts provenance information in two forms: a Provenance File or a free-text Provenance Description. Specification of the service can be found at: <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/user/dataset-management.html#dataset-versions>

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAoZCkLK6XUEm9UgabrjgVQL_DiK8oRP46lAoZnflPQM0/Dataverse_Support_Dataset_Versions

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ We use Dataverse to track changes to the metadata. Dataverse allows us to track the actions performed on the metadata and document the changes. A depositor or curator can add provenance metadata to a given file.

4

Declaration R1.2 Datasets: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?

Detailed provenance includes facets such as how the resource was generated, why it was generated, by whom, under what conditions, using what starting-data or source-resource, using what funding/resources, who owns the data, who should be given credit, and any filters or cleansing processes that have been applied post-generation. Provenance information helps people and machines assess whether a resource meets their criteria for their intended reuse, and what data manipulation procedures may be necessary in order to reuse it appropriately.

To summarize, this question requests a FAIR Enabling Resource of type “provenance model” which is a specification (schema) that defines metadata fields describing the origin and lineage of data or other digital objects. A prominent provenance model is PROV that can be used and implemented in metadata templates.

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Dataverse Support for Dataset Versions

Dataverse provides provenance facilities on dataset level and file level. A Dataverse installation accepts provenance information in two forms: a Provenance File or a free-text Provenance Description. Specification of the service can be found at: <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/user/dataset-management.html#dataset-versions>

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAoZCkLK6XUeM9UgabrJgVQL_DiK8oRP46IAoZnflPQM0/Dataverse_Support_Dataset_Versions

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

This question has not been answered yet!

5

Supporting Declaration R1.2: What provenance tracking service do you use to provide information about metadata and data?

A provenance tracking service is a system that systematically captures, stores and manages detailed information about the origin, history, and lifecycle of digital objects.

- a. Supporting Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

5.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

This question has not been answered yet!

6

Declaration R1.3: Your community uses this FAIR Implementation Profile to link to domain-relevant community standards. Please acknowledge this statement by clicking on 'Read and understood'.

Where community standards or best practices for data archiving and sharing exist, they should be followed. Several disciplinary communities have defined Minimal Information Standards describing the minimal set of metadata items required to assess the quality of the data acquisition and processing and to facilitate reproducibility. Such standards are a good start, noting that true (interdisciplinary) reusability will generally require richer metadata. For a list of such standards, consult for instance FAIRsharing.org. The required richness of the provenance metadata will be strongly dependent on the norms generated and agreed upon in the most related research communities.

When the FIP questionnaire is completed, and the resulting machine-readable FIP is published, it is considered to be the FAIR Enabling Resource for FAIR principle R1.3 and for this reason, there is no explicit question addressing this principle in the questionnaire. Hence, your FIP will be taken as the definitive list of domain-relevant community standards for your community, and could be used, for example, to inform automated FAIR evaluation services.

✓ a. Read and understood.

7

Supporting Declaration R1.3: What FAIR practice do you use for creating and maintaining metadata records ?

A (FAIR) practice is an adopted use of a specific protocol, guideline, procedure or workflow to support FAIRification, in this case for creating and maintaining metadata records, within a community.

✓ b. Supporting Declaration: FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

7.b.1

List the FAIR Supporting Resource(s)

Answers

7.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Supporting Resource

✓

DANS Data Stations Data Processing Manual

The manual contains information on how data is processed by DANS data station SSH.

- See metadata [here](#)
- See thing url: https://w3id.org/np/RAyYRyxAxzxpHBod0YTM01_94x6TOs59etOgVtsfd06rs/DANSDataProcessingManual

7.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

7.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this implementation choice.

- ✓ The manual can be found at: https://dans.knaw.nl/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/R.4.6.-Datastations-Data-Processing-Team-Handleiding_for-Publication-1.pdf

8

Supporting Declaration R1.3: What FAIR supporting software do you use?

A FAIR supporting software is any set of machine-readable instructions that supports the implementation of FAIR, that conform to a given syntax, that are interpretable by a given processor, and that instruct a computer's processor to perform specific tasks.

- ✓ a. Supporting Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

8.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

9

Supporting Declaration R1.3: Which FAIR Enrichment Service do you use?

A FAIR Enrichment Service is a service that enhances the FAIRness of existing resources through AI software with suggested semantic metadata and mappings.

- ✓ a. Supporting Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

9.a.1

Considerations (optional)

Please describe the community requirements and constraints leading to this answer.

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

VII. Register a new resource as a nanopublication

Why nanopublications?

If your resource is not already referenceable as a nanopublication you can create it here in the Wizard environment. The new nanopublication you create will register your resource by giving your resource a GUPRI (in the form of a Persistent URL or PURL) and a minimal metadata description. The nanopublication will allow your resource to be retrievable by the FIP Wizard in the drop-down lists of the answer field of the related question. As a nanopublication, your resource will also be considered by the GO FAIR Foundation for qualification assessment with respect to its Qualification Criteria. This procedure will require a few days. Nevertheless you can already use your newly minted nanopublication in the FIP Wizard or elsewhere.

Create new nanopublications

To create a nanopublication referencing your **FAIR Implementation Community (FIC)** please use this [template](#)

To create a nanopublication referencing your **FAIR-Enabling Resource (FER)** with metadata from a FAIRsharing record please use this [template](#)

To create a nanopublication referencing your **FAIR-Enabling Resource (FER) or other FAIR-Supporting Resource (FSR)** please use this [template](#)

Summary

Answered (current phase)	0 / 0	<div style="width: 0%;"></div>
Answered	0 / 0	<div style="width: 0%;"></div>

Questions

No questions